

**Republic of Yemen
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Research**

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The Verbal Inflection of the Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect

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**A Thesis submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements for the
Master's Degree of Linguistics and English Language Studies**

Deanship of Postgraduate Studies

Hadhramout University

December 2020

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my deepest gratitude and appreciation to everyone helped me to come up with this work. Foremost, my profound appreciation goes to my advisor Prof. Hassan Obeid Alfady whose encouragement and insightful comments were key factors to bring this work to life.

My sincere gratitude is extended to my workmates for their support and nobility. A big ‘thank you’ goes to my dearest classmate Mohammed Lahmadi for his assistance and moral support.

Last but not least, I would like to thank and honor my beloved family who always encourage me to study and succeed.

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List of Symbols and Abbreviations

1	First Person
2	Second Person
3	Third Person
//	Phonemic Transcription
[]	Phonetic Transcription
‘	English Translation of HEBD Forms
s.	Singular
pl.	Plural
m.	Masculan
f.	Feminin
NTM	Nonconactinative Templatic Morphology
SA	Standard Arabic
HA	Hadhami Arabic
HEBD	Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect
CHA	Costal Hadhami Arabic
VHA	Valley Hadhami Arabic
YADs	Yemeni Arabic Dialects

Abstract

The current study aims at exploring the Verbal inflection of one of the Hadhrami Arabic dialects namely Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect (Henceforth HEBD). The purpose of the study is (1) 1) To identify the verbal stems of HEBD.and (2) To describe how verbs of HEBD are inflected for gender, number and person. To accomplish these objectives the data were analyzed within the framework of the Nonconcatenative Templatic Morphology. McCarthy (1981) stated that Arabic exhibits a wide variety of nonconcatenative morphology: ablaut processes, apparent movements of segments to restructure canonical patterns, reduplication, and infixation. Being a descriptive, the study adopted the ethnographic qualitative design. The data of Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect were methodologically elicited by employing different methods, viz. Swadesh list, interviews, recordings, participant observations and oral morphology questionnaire which was designed and adapted from Dahl's, (1985), Bouquiaux and Thomas questionnaires (1992), Alfadly (2007) and Belleswed (2019). As a consequence, the elicited data revealed that each HEBD verb has two stems, one used for the perfect/past tense and one for the imperfect/present tense. It follows the Standard Arabic (SA) morphological system where the past tense stem takes suffixes in order to inflect, and the present tense stem takes both prefixes and suffixes (Ryding, 2005). However, some HEBD stems take different affixes from the ones used with SA stems when they get inflected. There are eight Measures with which the trilateral roots are interlocked to form stems. The quadrilateral roots are realized in only two specific Measures and a third one for the derived quadrilaterals. In the imperfective aspect, the

diphthong /ei/ is inserted as verbs are inflected for the 1st. and the 2nd. with reference to specific Measures.

Key words: Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect, Non-concatenative Templatic Morphology, Verbal Inflection, Arabic Verb Measures.

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

This chapter begins by providing an overview of the historical background of Semitic Languages. This is followed by highlighting the statement of the problem, the significance of the study, the limitation of the study and the purpose of the study including research questions and objectives. At the end of this chapter, definitions of key terms are addressed.

1.2. Historical Background

Arabic is a Semitic language akin to Hebrew, Aramaic, and Amharic, and more distantly related to indigenous language families of North Africa (Ryding, 2005). Historically, the Semitic family of languages, which by itself is one branch of the wider Afroasiatic group of languages, extended in the west from Sudan, Ethiopia, and Saudi Arabia in the south to what is today Syria in the north, and further east to what is today Iran and Iraq (Shimron, 2003). Besides those communities, Shimron (2003, Ibid) went on stating that communities of Semitic-speaking populations also exist in the Mediterranean (e.g. Malta), and along the northern coast of Africa (e.g. Morocco, Tunis, and Algeria) and claimed that the largest population of contemporary speakers of Semitic languages, in and out the ancient Semitic space, speak Arabic in its various dialects.

Redgarding the origins of Arabic language Versteegh (2014) pointed out that the Arabian peninsula had been inhabited from time immemorial by the 'lost Arabs' (*al-'Arab al-bā'ida*), that is, those tribes that are mentioned in the Quran as having been punished for their

disbelief, for instance, the tribes of ʿĀd, Ṭamūd and Jurhum. Versteegh (2014, p. 43) revealed further details on this matter stating that:

In this view, the later Arabs all descended from two ancestors, Qaḥṭān and ʿAdnān. Qaḥṭān was related to the ‘lost Arabs’, and his descendants were identified as the southern Arabs who were regarded as the ‘real Arabs’ (*al-ʿArab al-ʿarība*). The descendants of ʿAdnān were the northern Arabs, who were said to have been Arabicised at a later period (*al-ʿArab al-mutaʿarība* or *al-mustaʿarība*)

The ancient languages in central and northern Arabia are known as Ancient North Arabian; and those in the southwest Peninsula are classified as Ancient South Arabian (Al Mashaqba. 2015) Versteegh (2014, p. 44) pointed out that:

The descent of the northern Arabs was traced back through their ancestor ʿAdnān to ʿIsmāʿīl, the son of Abraham. Among the tribes descending from ʿAdnān were Huḍayl, Tamīm, Qays, Rabīʿa and the Qurayš of Mecca. Among the offspring of Qaḥṭān were the inhabitants of the South Arabian states, who were said to have descended from Ḥimyar, one of Qaḥṭān’s descendants. Some of the tribes in the northern part of the peninsula were of southern provenance, for instance, the ʿAws and Ḥazraj of Medina and the tribe Ṭayyiʿ

Macdonald (2000) as cited in Watson (2011) claimed that there are evidence from inscriptions that Arabic was used in some register or other in widely separated areas in the Arabian Peninsula in the centuries before the rise of Islam: the oldest Arabic inscription known to date is written in Sabaic script, which probably dates from the end of the first century BC. Before the rise of Islam, every tribe had its own dialect, which was a period of idol worship, but there evolved a common koine used by the ancient poets which helped the preservation of the language and assisted in its conservatism (Kaye, 2009). There was a

distinction in the *Jâhiliyya* between the everyday speech of the tribes and the language of poetry and the *Qur'ân* (Ryding, 2005). With respect to this view, there has been a debate centered around the existence and use of desinential (i.e., word-final) case and mood inflection, a central feature of classical poetry but one which fell increasingly out of use in spoken Arabic, and which no longer exists in the urban vernaculars of today (Ibid). Kaye (2009) added the loss of the dual in the verb, adjective and pronoun; and the loss of mood distinctions in the verb to what the modern Arabic dailects have lost.

Watson (2002) argues that the expansion of Islam throughout the Peninsula, north into the Levant, east into Iraq and Khuzistan, and west into North Africa, was not only a religious and hence cultural conquest, but also a linguistic conquest, and within a few hundred years Arabic became both the official and the vernacular language of all Islamicized countries in the Middle East. Arabic became an international language of civilization, culture, scientific writing and research, diplomacy, and administration (Ryding, 2005).

2.1.1 General background on HEBD.

HEBD is a Hadhrami Arabic dialect. It is spoken in the eastern part of the costal Hadhrami areas. The people of the target dialect are bedouins living in a small village called Halfoon. This village is situated near the city of AdDis Alsharqiah. There are approximately two thousand speakers of HEBD live in Halfoon. Bahumaid (2015) claimed that within Hadhrami Arabic, two broad varieties may be distinguished: Coastal Hadhrami Arabic, spoken in the coastal areas of Hadhramout and Wadi Hadhrami Arabic, spoken in towns and villages in “interior Hadhramout.” Through out this study, the researcher will prove that HEBD exhibits

is attributed to contactual phenomena which are often facilitated by migrations involving the settlement of bedouin groups near or in rural or urban areas, or the settlement of rural segments near or in urban centers (ibid). Many of the Bedouins of the target dialect left the mountains and settled in urban areas or near in the forms of small villages. This case of close contact with the urban areas is considered to be a serious threat to the existence of the HEBD because the coming generations will lose many if not all of the linguistic features of their own dialect.

From long time ago, people of Hadhramout are well known of their emigrations to neighboring and overseas countries for trading. About the Hadhrami dialect, Al-Sqqaf (2006) stated that it is also spoken by many Yemeni emigrants who migrated from Hadhramout to East Africa (Kenya, Somalia and Tanzania), South-east Asia (Indonesia, Malaysia, Brunei and Singapore) and, recently, to the Arabian Gulf countries. This openness brought new words that are used instead of the original words of the dialect. Bedouins go to Saudi Arabia or other Arab countries and stay there for long time do not use their own dialect. Therefore, when they come back they use, maybe involuntary, the vocabulary and the grammar they have used in that country which become fixed within time. TVs have entered the most houses of the Bedouins in the past ten years. People watching TV shows and being exposed to other Arabic dialects repeatedly are more expected to lose their own dialect.

Although it has a unique system, there has been no attempt to document any linguistic aspect of HEBD. This may be due to the fact that the speakers of the target dialect are not open to the outer world until recently. This study is considered to be the first one about HEBD. It investigates one of the most important linguistic aspect of

HEBD which is its verbal inflection. It will also help preserving the original linguistic state of HEBD. Last but not least, it will be a valuable addition to the small number of current literature of the Hadhrami Arabic dialects studies.

1.4 The Objectives of the Study

This study is being done to achieve the following objectives:

- 1) To identify the verbal stems of HEBD.
- 2) To describe how verbs of HEBD are inflected for gender, number and person.

1.4.1 The Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

- 1) What are the verbal stems of HEBD?
- 2) How are verbs of HEBD inflected for gender, number and person?

1.5. The Significance of the Study

This study would be one of the few studies about one of the Arabic dialects in Hadhramout, Yemen. It is considered to be first one about the Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect. It will show the unique system of HEBD. Those who are interested in linguistics and morphology are expected to value this study. It tackles the verbal inflection of HEBD following educational research system and using the nonconcatenative templatic morphology. Researchers are provided with the basis for further investigation regarding HEBD linguistic system.

1.6. The Limitations of the Study

This study is limited to describe the verbal inflection of the Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin dialect. It focuses on describing how verbs are inflected for gender, number and person. Verbs are the main concern of this study. This research is limited to study the spoken bedouin dialect of Hadhrami people who live only in Ad Dis Alsharqiah, specifically, in the village of Halfoon.

1.7. The Definition of the Terms

1.7.1. Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect:

HEBD is a dialect spoken in many areas along the coastline of Hadhramout. People who speak this dialect are supposed to be living in the mountains or in some villages that lay near the cities.

1.7.2. Stem:

The stem of a word is the word form minus its inflectional affixes (Booij, 2007).

1.7.3. Root

Erwin (n.d) as cited in Ryding (2005) defined a root as a relatively invariable discontinuous bound morpheme, represented by two to five phonemes, typically three consonants in a certain order, which interlocks with a pattern to form a stem and which has lexical meaning. Aronoff (1994) claimed that the traditional technical sense of this term as denoting the ultimate elements from which words are derived, which goes back centuries, is fairly clear (though it may or may not be theoretically valid). According to

Booij (2007), roots may be turned into stems by the addition of a morpheme.

1.7.4. Pattern

A pattern is a bound and in many cases, discontinuous morpheme consisting of one or more vowels and slots for root phonemes (radicals), which either alone or in combination with one to three derivational affixes, interlocks with a root to form a stem, and which generally has grammatical meaning (Erwin as cited in Ryding ,2005). In phonology, the term has been used to refer specifically to any neatness of arrangement that can be demonstrated in a sound system – a unit such as a phoneme being seen as a point in a pattern of sound relationships (Crystal, 2008). According to most linguistics, the root usually carries the core meaning of the word, while the word pattern creates variations on its meaning, and determines the word class and other grammatical characteristics (Deutsch and Frost, 2003).

1.7.5 Prefix

A prefix is a bound morpheme added to the beginning of a word (e.g. unhappy) (Yule, 2010).

1.7.6 Suffix

It is a bound morpheme added to the end of a word (e.g. fainted, illness) (Yule , 2010).

1.7.7 Infix

An infix is a type of bound morpheme that is inserted into the middle of the stem (Dawson and Phelan, 2016).

1.7.8 Gender

A grammatical category used for the analysis of word-classes displaying such contrasts as masculine (m, masc, MASC), feminine (f, F, fem, FEM) and neuter (n, neut, NEUT), animate and inanimate, etc (Crystal, 2008).

1.7.9 Number

A grammatical category used for the analysis of word classes displaying such contrasts as singular (sg, SG, sing), plural (pl, PL), dual (du) ('two'), trial ('three'), paucal ('few'), etc., as in English boy v. boys, he walks v. they walk (Crystal, 2008).

1.7.10 Person

A category used in grammatical description to indicate the number and nature of the participants in a situation (Crystal, 2008). Yule (2010) pointed out that the grammatical category distinguishing first person (involving the speaker, me), second person (involving the hearer, you) and third person (involving any others, she, them).

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the main terms and the theoretical framework that have been applied in this study are defined and explained. Starting with defining morphology in general then a brief description of Arabic morphology is provided. The basic principles of Non-concatenative Templatic Morphology are considered to be the theoretical framework of this study as they have been defined and explained below. At the end of this chapter the researcher turns to the previous studies that have been conducted on the field of Yemeni dialects.

2.2 Morphology

Morphology is the study of word formation, including the ways new words are coined in the languages of the world, and the way forms of words are varied depending on how they are used in sentences (Lieber, 2009). As a native speaker of your language, you have intuitive knowledge of how to form new words, and every day you recognize and understand new words that you have never heard before (Ibid). Radford, Atkinson, Britain, Clahsen, and Spencer (2009) defined morphology as the field of linguistics that examines the internal structure of words and processes of word formation.

Yule (2010) pointed out that in many languages, what appear to be single forms actually turn out to contain a large number of “word-like” elements. For example, in Swahili (spoken throughout East Africa), the form *nitakupenda* conveys what, in English, would

have to be represented as something like *I will love you* (Ibid). This morphological phenomenon could be found in HEBD too. For instance, the form {bamkhash} would be translated by a bunch of separated words, *I will do more*. In addition, it has a pragmatic meaning which depends on the time of speaking and the action at that moment. If a speaker was cooking rice and said {bamkhash}, that means he/she would add more rice. If a speaker was buying something and said it, it would mean he/she would buy more of that thing and so on.

Tracing the history of the term morphology, McCarthy (2002) stated that the area of grammar concerned with the structure of words and with relationships between words involving the morphemes that compose them is technically called morphology, from the Greek word *morphe* ‘form, shape’; and morphemes can be thought of as the minimal units of morphology. Booij (2007, p. 6) added that:

The term ‘morphology’ has been taken over from biology where it is used to denote the study of the forms of plants and animals. Its first recorded use is in writings by the German poet and writer Goethe in 1796. It was first used for linguistic purposes in 1859 by the German linguist August Schleicher (Salmon 2000), to refer to the study of the form of words. In present-day linguistics, the term ‘morphology’ refers to the study of the internal structure of words, and of the systematic form–meaning correspondences between words.

Derivation, since it is the process of creating words or lexical units, is considered procedurally prior to inflection, which subsequently acts upon the word stem and modifies it, if necessary, for use in context (by affixing /-s/ in English for plural, for example, or /-ed/ for past tense) (Ryding, 2005).

Aronoff (1994) suggested that we should consider first Bloomfield's definition of morphology from the opening sentences of his classic chapter on morphology: "By the morphology of a language we mean the constructions in which bound forms appear among the constituents. By definition, the resultant forms are either bound forms or words, but never phrases (Ibid). Morphology has two main branches derivational morphology and inflectional morphology (Thakur, 1997).

2.2.1 Derivational Morphology

Derivational morphology refers to the study of how morphemes are combined to form new words (Thakur 1997). New lexemes that are formed with prefixes and suffixes on a base are often referred to as derived words, and the process by which they are formed as derivation (Lieber, 2009).

Anderson (1992, p. 185) clarified that:

The differences between inflectional and derivational rules are thus in their substantive specification. On one hand, the Structural Descriptions of inflectional rules refer to properties of Morphosyntactic Representations, while the Structural Descriptions of derivational rules refer to the content of (classes of) lexical items. On the other, the Structural Changes of inflectional rules affect only their phonological form, while derivational rules typically also effect modification in an item's semantics and/or syntax as well.

2.2.2 Inflectional Morphology

Inflectional morphology is a study of how words change their form to indicate number, person, tense, etc (Thakur, 1997). The set {print, prints, printing, printed} comprises all the word-forms of the verb lexeme PRINT. However as Hippiley and Stump (2016) pointed out

we would not normally want to say that printable is a “form” of the verb to print (or vice versa)—that is, the form printable is not a member of the inflectional paradigm of the lexeme PRINT. Instead we generally say that the lexeme PRINTABLE has been derived from the base lexeme PRINT by a word formation process, or, more accurately, a process of lexeme formation (Ibid). Lieber (2009) described inflectional morphology as inflectional word formation and clarified that inflectional word formation is word formation that expresses grammatical distinctions like number (singular *vs.* plural); tense (present *vs.* past); person (first, second, or third); and case (subject, object, possessive), among others. It does not result in the creation of new lexemes, but merely changes the grammatical form of lexemes to fit into different grammatical contexts (Ibid).

Derivation and inflection are both restricted to morphology in the narrow sense of morphological realization, but they differ from one another on the basis of what they realize: lexeme-internal versus lexeme-external syntactic elements (Aronoff, 1994). It has long been observed that in forms where both derivational and inflectional morphology are overtly represented, material corresponding to productive inflection comes "outside of other morphology (Anderson, 1992). That is, where two or more suffixes are involved, inflectional ones come after derivational ones; and where prefixes are involved, inflectional ones come before derivational ones (Ibid).

2.3 Arabic Morphology

Unlike the more familiar basically concatenative morphology of the Indo-European languages, Semitic morphology is pervaded by a wide variety of purely morphological alternations internal to the stem (McCarthy, 1981). Because of its almost (too perfect) algebraic-looking grammar, i.e. root and pattern morphology, Arabic, sticks out like a sore thumb in comparative Semitic linguistics (Kaye, 2009).

Ali (1988) as cited in Abuata and Al-Omari (2015) pointed out that the grammatical system of the Arabic language is based on a root-and-pattern structure and considered as a root-based language with not more than 10,000 roots. The root in most word of the language is a semantic abstraction consisting of three consonants from which actual words are derived by the superimposition of templatic patterns (Holes, 2004). On the morphological system of semitic languages like Hebrew and Arabic, Fromkin et al, (2014) illustrated this morphological process by providing an example claiming that the root for ‘write’ in Egyptian Arabic is *ktb*, from which the following words (among others) are formed by infixing vowels:

katab ‘he wrote’

kaatib ‘writer’

kitáab ‘book’

kútub ‘books’

According to Davis and Tsujimura (2014). two types of nonconcatenative processes that are characteristic of Arabic are stem modification and templatic morphology Morphologists

see stem modification as difficult to accommodate in a concatenation-based model (Anderson, 1992).

Although this study will not be about the differences between the Standard Arabic and HEBD, the researcher thought it would be better to provide an example. About the Standard Arabic morphology, Ryding (2005) pointed out that it consists primarily of a system of consonant roots which interlock with patterns of vowels (and sometimes certain other consonants) to form words, or word stems. Throughout this study it would be clear that in HEBD some vowels, that are used in certain Standard Arabic forms, are dropped out and some patterns are not used at all. The following example will clarify:

Table 2. 1 An example from Standard Arabic Measures

Roots	Patterns	Derived Forms
فعل [fʕl]	فَعَلَ [faʕal]	كَتَبَ [kataba] ‘(He) wrote’
	فِعَال [fiʕa:l]	كِتَاب [kita:b] ‘A book’
	فُعِلَ [fuʕil]	كُتِبَ [kutib] ‘was written’

Table 2. 2: An example from HEBD Measures

Roots	Patterns	Derived Forms
فعل [fʕl]	فَعَلَ [faʕal]	كَتَبَ [ktab] ‘(He) wrote’
	فِعَال [fiʕa:l]	كِتَاب [kta:b] ‘A book’
	فُعِلَ [fuʕil]	Not used

The first vowel /a/ in the form [kataba] is dropped out as well as the first vowel /i/ in the form [kita:b]. The passive pattern is not used in HEBD.

Levin (2011) pointed out that the Arab grammarians' concept of the individually smallest meaningful elements in Arabic language basically accords with the modern concept of morpheme, although they divide such units into two groups: *kalim* and *zawā'id*. Analysis of the data gathered from the *Kitāb* shows that] Sībawayh's distinction between morphemes classified as *kalim* and morphemes classified as *zawā'id* derives mainly from morphological considerations, and from the notion that etymologically, the essence of the sounds composing morphemes classified as *kalim* differs from that of the sounds composing morphemes classified as *zawā'id*: the sounds composing morphemes classified as *zawā'id* belong to the category of sounds called *az-zawā'id* or *ḥurūf az-zawā'id*, while those composing morphemes classified as *kalim* do not belong to any specific category of sounds, i.e., they do not belong to any of the categories of sounds composing nouns and verbs, known by the terms *ḥurūf 'uṣūl*, *ḥurūf az-zawā'id* and *ḥurūf al-badal* (Ibid).

2.3.1 Arabic Verbs

Arabic verbs fall into two major groups, those with three-consonant roots (trilateral) and those with four-consonant roots (quadrilateral) (Ryding, 2005). Around each lexical root is structured a set of possible stem classes or verb forms (normally ten for trilateral roots and four for quadrilateral) (Ibid). It is important to know and recognize the root of every verb, because the root is the invariable basis of all the different forms of the verb, as well as of most nouns, adjectives, adverbs, and even many prepositions (Abu-Chacra, 2018).

Arabic exhibits rich subject-verb agreement morphology: the verb shares with the subject the feature agreement of person, number and gender (Alhawary, 2007). When Arabic verbs inflect for those morphological categories, these inflections are marked by means of prefixes, suffixes, changes in vowel pattern, and stem changes (Ryding, 2005).. Because there is no infinitive in Arabic in the same sense as in English, the third person masculine singular of the perfect tense is given as the corresponding basic or reference form of the verb (Abu-Chacra, 2018).

There are two basic morphological tenses in Arabic: past and present, also called perfective and imperfective, respectively (Ryding,). The tenses in Arabic do not express the time of an event in the same precise way as the primary tenses in Indo-European languages (Abu-Chacra, 2018). The Arabic verb expresses the state rather than the action or event (sterling, 1904) That is why the terms perfect and imperfect tense do not correspond to the meaning of these terms in, for example, English (Abu-Chacra, 2018).

2.4. The Theoretical Background

2.4.1 Non-Concatenative Templatic Morphology

It is a prosodic theory in the sense that it uses the devices of autosegmental phonology, which are most familiar through studies of tone and other prosody (McCarthy, 1981). Davis and Tsujimura (2014) pointed out that McCarthy's early work focused on the root and pattern morphology of Semitic in which the prosodic template itself contributes to the meaning of the word. This approach treats templates as pieces of representation, an empty skeletal frame into which the vowels and consonants of a given morpheme or stem or word must fit (Inkelas, 2014). According to the traditional view of Semitic non-concatenative

morphology, a word such as Arabic *takattab* ‘got written’ is made up of the consonantal “root” /ktb/ and a melodic verbal “template” (alternatively called Pattern, Measure, Form, *wazn* or *binyan*) (Kastner, 2018). This idea was famously formalized by McCarthy (1979, 1981), who divided the Semitic verb into three “planes” or “tiers”: the CV skeleton (slots for consonant and vowels), the root (consonants) and the melody (individual vowels and inflectional information) (Ibid). Templatic morphology is pervasive in both nouns and verbs of Semitic languages, but the verbal systems are particularly striking because of their root-and-pattern system of non-concatenative morphology (Davis and Tsujimura, 2014). According to Haile and Al Mtenje (1988) Nonconcatenative morphology defines morphological structure in which morphemes cannot be so easily broken down into separate recurring elements capable of being added linearly either to the left or to the right of their base. It is this type of morphological patterning, characteristic of most Semitic languages, and its concomitant problems for which McCarthy (1979, 1981, and later publications) proposed an autosegmental analysis (Ibid). Following McCarthy's (1979) influential study, many phonologists and morphologists assume the consonantal root-based approach as the only possible analysis of word formation in Semitic languages. In this view, the consonantal root, the vocalic melody and the prosodic template occupy separate tiers (as an extension of the notion tier from Autosegmental Phonology (Goldsmith 1976)) (Ussishkin, 2005). Watson (2002) elaborated on this matter stating that the stem of a content word in Arabic has three discontinuous morphemes: the consonantal root, which is the fundamental lexical unit of the language (McCarthy and Prince 1990a: 2); the templatic pattern into which the consonantal root is inserted imposing an additional meaning to that of the root; and the intercalated vowels (the vocalic melody) which mark variations in, for example, the voice (active or passive) in verbs, agentive relations in nouns derived from

verbs, and singular–plural relations in nouns. In the following figure a non-linear representation of the HEBD verb /kəmməl/ ‘to finish’.

Figure 2. 1: Non-Linear representation of the HEBD verb / kmml/

2.5 Previous Studies

There are diffrenet studies conducted on Arabic dialects. Tucker (2011) investigated Iraqi Arabic Verbs using the Root and Prosody Approach. He came to a conclusion that the only difference in Root and Prosody approach between NTM and non-NTM languages is constraint ranking, the basic typological control in Optimality Theory (Prince & Smolensky, 1993/2004).

Lahrouchi and Lampitelli (2017) studied the phonology of vebral inflection of Moroccan Arabic and Tashlhiyt Berber. They found out that:

- Weak and sound verbs behave invariable with respect to inflection.
- Surface differences result from templatic constraints

- Apophony underlies the melodic expression of person in MA
- Weak verbs retrieve I and A as a mean to distinguish 3 person from 1 and 2 person.

Regarding Yemeni dialects, Abdulghani (2010) pointed out that few methodological studies are available on Arabic dialects particularly on Yemeni Arabic dialects (YADs). In her famous book, Watson (2002) described the phonology and morphology of Sana'a and Cairene. It is one of the best valuable studies conducted on a Yemeni dialect. She argued that prosodic morphology of Cairene and San'ani should be analysed in terms of two morphological levels. I then described a number of level-one processes in the two dialects. In general, levelone processes equate with the nonconcatenative morphology and level-two processes with the concatenative morphology.

Regarding the Hadhrami dialects, Al-Saqqaf (1999) conducted a study describing the morphology of the spoken Arabic of Wadi Hadhramout. According to Belleswed (2019) It is to be the only full work on the morphological aspect of VHA though Al-Saqqaf in this work frequently referred to some linguistic aspects of the coastal dialects.

Bahameed (2007) discussed the translatability of the Hadhrami proverbial expressions. He investigating how the subcultural Hadhrami proverbial expressions could be translated, with the view to describe and explain the translation processes utilizing think-aloud protocols for data collection and analysis. The findings of the study were that Hadhrami proverbial expressions are translatable by applying three equivalence theories and these are functional, ideational and formal with the ideational equivalence being the most applicable. The study concludes with a translating idiographic 'theory' comprising, a subjective

strategy, which focuses on the cognitive processes that influence the translator's decision-making. It also comprises an objective strategy, which offers nine formulae as practical solutions for the problems of translating the Hadhrami proverbial expressions.

Al-Tairi (2010) handled the consonant clusters in the Mukallaene Arabic (MA). His study provided preliminary observations and analysis within Optimality Theory (OT) (Prince & Smolensky 1993, 2004). He claimed that, in MA, consonant clusters occur as onsets in the syllable, but not as codas. According to him, the sequencing of consonants does not depend on factors such as sonority rise, place/manner of articulation, or voicing assimilation and Complex codas are prohibited and are separated by an epenthetic vowel. He argued that geminates are immune to epenthesis and they occur word-medially and finally

Bahumaid (2015) investigated the English loanwords that have penetrated the lexicon of the Arabic vernacular of Hadramout over the past few decades. The study provided sufficient evidence of the lexical expansion of Hadhrami Arabic through borrowings from English especially in electric, mechanical and vehicles-related fields. He collected a total of 125 English-originated words in Hadhrami Arabic from oral and printed sources. The analysis has shown that phonological adaptation of those loanwords to the HA structure has involved certain processes including sound nativization, the pharyngealization, gemination, metathesis and some consonants as well as the insertion of a vowel to break the word-initial consonant cluster.

Belleswed (2019) investigated Coastal Hadhrami Arabic verbal morphology. She concentrated on the Arabic urban variety spoken in the coastal area of Hadhramout province, exactly the main cities on the coast of Hadhramout: Mukalla and Shihr. The findings of the

study showed that CHA is a rich dialect with verbal morphology in which nearly all stems of Arabic are used except Stem IV. The analysis of underived stems of verbs reveals that these forms undergo a process of deletion, indicating the lower status of the constraint MAX-IO and in some cases the epenthesis takes place violating the low ranking constraint DEPIO. On the other hand, the analysis of the derived stems depends mostly on the alignment constraints that modify the prosodic structure of the verb either by changing the vocalic pattern or by affixation.

The current study is considered to be the first one that deals with the verbal inflection of HEBD which is spoken by the bedouins of Ghail Bin Yumain and the eastern villages along Hadhramout coast.

2.6 The Conceptual Framework of the Study

The theory of Root and Pattern Morphology (Nonconcatenative) McCarthy (1981) has been adopted as the Framework of this current study. It has been presented and discussed early. Figure 2.2 represents the elements of the conceptual framework of the study which is conceptualised to achieve the research objectives and answer the research questions.

Figure 2.2: The conceptual framework of the study

Chapter 3

RESEARCH METHDOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

At the beginning of this chapter, the researcher states the research design which was adopted in this study and through which the questions of this study were answered. Then the sampling and the process of the selection of informants are explained. How the data were collected and how they were analyzed is stated at the end of this chapter.

3.2 Research Design

In this study, the researcher adopted a qualitative ethnographic design. It enables the researcher to collect the data by being part of the target population, in this case the people who speak the target dialect, and to get the opportunity to closely observe the informants. Ethnographic designs are qualitative procedures for describing, analyzing, and interpreting a shared style of behavior, beliefs, and language of a specific community that develop over time (Creswell, 2012). Yin (2011) defined ethnography as a field-based study of people in their real life, usually occurring over a sufficiently long period of time to reveal people's everyday routines—that is, their norms, rituals, and acceptable social interactions, and establishing the distinctiveness of their culture.

The core strategy in the field methods used in ethnography is the direct observation of naturally occurring in situ actions; additional strategies include informal and formal interviews, the collection of documents and artifacts, and the making of field recordings (Ten

Have, 2004). Alfadly (2007) pointed out that it is implicitly stated in Jones (2004) that extensive use of unstructured observations and conversations documented by detailed field notes form the basis for this type of research, often considered the purest form of qualitative research. The researcher's own experiences inevitably also play a role, whether explicit or implicit (Ten Have, 2004, Ibid).

3.2. Sampling and Selection of Informants

The quality of a piece of research stands or falls by the appropriateness of its methodology and instrumentation and by the suitability of the sampling strategy that has been adopted (Cohen, Manion and Morrison. 2018). Buchstaller and Khattab (2013) stated that the most reliable method for finding out about the language use of a particular group of people would be to collect linguistic information from every single person in the population, which in the social sciences refers to all members of the community. Obviously, except for very small populations, this method is rather impractical, expensive, and time consuming (Ibid). An optimum sample is one which fulfills the requirements of efficiency, representativeness, reliability and flexibility (Kothari, 2004) which is originated from a subgroup of people that reflects the population as a whole (in terms of their social and linguistic characteristics) (Buchstaller and Khattab, 2013).

There are two main methods of sampling. According to Cohen et al, (2018) the researcher must decide whether to opt for a probability (also known as a random sample) or a non-probability sample (also known as a purposive sample). Qualitative research uses non-probability samples for selecting the population for study (Ritchie, Lewis and Elam, 2003). In a non-probability sample, units are deliberately selected to reflect particular features of or groups within the sampled population (Ibid).

Purposive sampling is adopted in this study. Dutta (2016) pointed out that Sampling in ethnographic research relies primarily on purposive and criterion-based sampling techniques. According to Ritchie et al, (2003) Burgess (1984) and Honigmann (1982) call this judgement sampling and LeCompte and Preissle (1993) maintain that criterion based is a more appropriate term than purposive because all sampling is purposive, but purposive is the term most commonly used in the literature.

Milroy (1987) as cited in Alfadly (2007) stated that the principle underlying judgment sampling is that “the researcher identifies in advance the types of speakers to be studied and then seeks out a quota of speakers who fit the specified categories”. Ritchie et al, (2003) pointed out that the sample units are chosen because they have particular features or characteristics which will enable detailed exploration and understanding of the central themes and puzzles which the researcher wishes to study. Members of a sample are chosen with a 'purpose' to represent a location or type in relation to a key criterion (Ibid).

The following criteria were given priority in choosing the informants:

- 1) Locally based: born, raised and presently living in the area of the target dialect (geographical area: location).
- 2) Target dialect spoken in informal domains of use.
- 3) Stability: the informants have not lived away from hometown for a long period of time (to elicit more authentic and natural language use).

Due to the conservative nature of the community where the target dialect is spoken, women would not agree to talk with a stranger. Therefore, the participants included only

males between the ages of 20-30, 33-50, and 61-76. eleven participants in total were chosen to be representative of the HEBD. Of these eleven participants, two were of the age bracket 20-30; six were of the age bracket 33-50; and three were of the age bracket of 61-76. The following table simplifies this matter.

Table 3. 2 Distribution of Participants

Age	The number of the participants
20-30	2
33-50	6
61-76	3
Total	10

The following table was designed to provide more detailed information about the chosen informants. It displays the distribution of participants from HEBD by birthdate, level of education, and residence history

Table 3. 3 Detailed Distribution of Participants by Speaker, Level of education and Residence

Speaker	Birthdate Level of education	Resedence
1	1955 Illiterate	Born and raised in Halfoon. In 1974 (19 years old) traveled to Kwait to work and commuted between kwait and yemen until 1990. Currently resides in Halfoon and works in his grocery store.

2	1977 Eighth grade	Born and raised in Halfoon. Used to work as a fisherman since 1998 (21 years old) until 2017 (40 years old).
3	1945 Illiterate	Born and raised in halfoon. Has not left halfoon for more than a week. In the last twenty years, he works in his own clothes shop and commutes daily between Halfoon and AdDis Alsharqiah. .
4	1983 Seventh grade	Born and raised in Halfoon. Used to work in a company in Alsheher since 1998 to 2006. Currently, he runs a restaurant in AdDis Alsharqiah.
5	1975 Secondary school	Born and raised in Halfoon. In 2001 (26 years old), Commuted daily between AdDis Alsharqiah and Halfoon to study. Then, he commuted between Saudi Arabia and Yemen to work until 2011. Since then, he works in a company in Mukalla and stays in Halfoon in the weekends.
6	1994 Sixth grade	Born and raised in Halfoon. Has not left halfoon for more than a week. Works as builder.
7	1992 Nineth grade	Born and raised in Halfoon. Commuted between Halfoon and Qusair since 2017 (25 years old) until 2020 (29 years old). Currently, he resides and works in Halfoon.
8	1977 Secondary school	Born and raised in Halfoon. Commuted daily between halfoon and AdDis

		Alsharqiah to study. Graduated from the secondary school in 1996 (19 years old). Then, he worked with fishermen; cooking food for them while they go fishing. Currently, he commuted between Halfoon and Mukalla working as a chef.
9	1988 Secondary school	Born and raised in Halfoon. Commuted daily between halfoon and AdDis Alsharqiah to study. He worked as an engineer with small companies in Al-Raidah and Qusair until 2019. Since then, he works in Mukalla and goes back to Halfoon in weekends.
10	1971 BA	Born and raised in Halfoon. In 1992 (21 years old) moved to Sana'a to study. In 1996 moved back to Halfoon and currently resides there.
11	1960 Illiterate	Born and raised in Halfoon. Since 1982 (22 years old) until 1990 (30 years old), he commuted between yemen and. Currently, he works in Alsheher and stay in Halfoon in weekends.

3.3. Data Collection

As this study has been conducted to investigate the verbal inflection of HEBD, almost all the data are verbs, phrases or lexemes of daily usage in the life of the people of the target dialect. Different tools were used in collecting the data for this study but among them all

and the most productive sources is the researcher being a native speaker. The researcher as being a native speaker used his intuitive knowledge of the dialect for data collection.

As there are no previous work that was conducted on HEBD, the researcher relied on primary sources such as the Swadesh List and oral morphology questionnaire which was designed and adapted from Dahl's, (1985), Bouquiaux and Thomas questionnaires (1992), and Alfadly (2007) to help collecting more reliable data. Alfadly (2007) pointed out that Henry (2005) came to a conclusion that oral questionnaire is a suitable method of obtaining judgments on nonstandard varieties, because these varieties are not generally written. Presentation of non-standard sentences in a written form seems strange to native speakers, because, unfortunately, they never see them written (Polleto and Cornips, 2005 as cited in Alfadly, Ibid). Thus, oral questioning is essential. The main part of this oral questionnaire consists of a number of sentences. These sentences were translated into Arabic by the researcher. The questionnaire was designed to elicit details of verbal inflection in HEBD. The following data of verbal classes in HEBD were requested:

1. Roots
2. Vocalic patterns
3. Stems
4. Verbal templates

The researcher conducted face-to-face interviews which according to Creswell (2012) occurs when researchers ask one or more participants general, open-ended questions and record their answers. The researcher then transcribes and types the data into a computer file for analysis (Ibid). Typed records were used in recording informal and indirect interviews

with the people of the target dialect. Legard, Keegan and Ward (2003) stated that it is highly desirable to audio-record the interview and for the researcher to take few if any notes during the interview. This allows the researcher to devote his or her full attention to listening to the interviewee and probing in-depth (Ibid). The researcher made sure to include data from a variety of speakers. As Chelliah (2013) clarified the goal of language description is often not to capture just one speaker's internal grammar but to represent prevalent patterns for a community of speakers.

3.4. Method of Analysis

As previously noted, this study is primarily a qualitative descriptive study of verbal inflection of HEBD. There are two exciting facets of language description: the fieldwork experience, which is necessary for data collection, and the process of discovery and analysis that leads to the description of the target language (Chelliah, 2013). Creswell (2014) stated that data analysis in qualitative research will proceed hand-in-hand with other parts of developing the qualitative study, namely, the data collection and the write-up of findings. The phases are also iterative, meaning you cycle back and forth between data collection and analysis (Creswell, 2012). In doing so, the researcher was able to examine the collected data frequently and avoid any unintentional breaches of ethics in data analysis which according to Cohen et al. (2018) must not mis-present findings or the phenomenon itself and researchers must be vigilant, very self-aware and reflexive in their data analysis. The data in the current study were transcribed and analyzed according to Non Concatenative Templatic Morphology Theory. Oral morphology questionnaire data and spontaneous speech data were transcribed in fine phonetic transcription. In chapter 5, each Sound verb was interpreted in a non-linear presentation.

Chapter 4

The Phonology of HEBD

4.1 The Phonemic Inventory of HEBD

According to MacCarthy (1993) the study of reduplicative and root-and-pattern morphology has emerged in recent years as a touchstone for the relation between the theory of phonology and the theory of word formation. Even if phonology and morphology are conceptualized as distinct grammatical modules, they are constantly intermingling (Inkelas, 2014). Morphological and phonological systems are often conceived of in linear terms: the concatenation of one morpheme to another, or the assimilation of a feature from one segment to an adjacent one, play a central role in describing the structures generated by the

grammar of a language (Kastner, 2019). In this Chapter, an introductory survey of HEBD phonemic system has been basically presented so as to help the reader to go smoothly through Chapters 5 and 6.

4.1.1 HEBD Consonants

To identify the consonants of HEBD, the minimal pair procedure is used. According to Yule (2010) phonemic distinctions in a language can be tested via pairs and sets of words. When two words such as pat and bat are identical in form except for a contrast in one phoneme, occurring in the same position, the two words are described as a minimal pair. (Ibid). Different frames are used. The first frame is /-ɜ:b/. Only ten consonants form meaningful words in this frame. In order for the consonants to form meaningful words, another frame is used. The other frame is /-ad/. Eight consonants form meaningful words in this frame. For the rest of the consonants two other frames are used; /-lam/ and /-as^ɕ/. Four consonants form meaningful words in the first one and three in the second one. Examples related to this are provided in the following tables.

Table 4. 1: Minimal pairs test of HEBD consonants

The phoneme	Example	Gloss
/b/	/bɜ:b/	‘door’
/t/	/tɜ:b/	‘to repent’
/ð/	/ðɜ:b/	‘to melt’
/n/	/nɜ:b/	‘to represent’
/s/	/sɜ:b/	‘to leave’
/z/	/zɜ:b/	‘to be riotous’
/ʃ/	/ʃɜ:b/	‘to fault’
/j/	/jɜ:b/	‘to bring’

/tˤ/	/tˤɜːb/	‘to be healing’
/h/	/hɜːb/	‘to be in love’

Table 4. 2: Minimal pairs test of HEBD consonants

The phoneme	Example	Gloss
/j/	/jad/	‘hand’
/k/	/kad/	‘to work hard’
/sˤ/	/sˤəd/	‘to block’
/ʃ/	/ʃad/	‘to pull’
/m/	/mad/	‘to shake hands’
/χ/	/χad/	‘to take’
/ɾ/	/rad/	‘to replay’

Table 4. 3: Minimal pairs test of HEBD consonant

The phoneme	Example	Gloss
/ʔ/	/ʔam/	‘or’
/dˤ/	/dˤam/	‘to hug’
/w/	/wam/	‘to expect’
/θ/	/θam/	‘there’
/d/	/dam/	‘blood’

Table 4. 4: Minimal pairs test of HEBD consonants

The phoneme	Example	Gloss
/f/	/fasˤ/	‘to squeeze’
/g/	/gasˤ/	‘to cut/
/l/	/lasˤ/	‘to turn on’
/ɣ/	/ɣasˤ/	‘to choke’

/h/	/has ^s /	‘to
-----	---------------------	-----

There are twenty seven phonemes in HBED. They are distributed as follows: eight stops (/b/, /t/, /t^s/, /d/, /d^s/, /k/, /g/, and /ʔ/), twelve fricatives (/θ/, /ð/, /f/, /s/, /s^s/, /z/, /ʃ/, /ç/, /ʝ/, /ħ/, /ʕ/ and /h/), one affricative (/j/), two nasals (/m/ and /n/), one approximant (/l/) and one trill (/r/). /j/ and /j/ are allophones. /j/ is used by those who still live far from the urban. Those who live in villages near the urban usually use /j/ instead.

Table 4. 5: Consonant system of HBED

Place Manner	Labial	Dental	Alveolar		Palate- alveolar	Palatal	Velar	Uvular	Pharyn- geal	Glottal
			Plain	emphatic						
Nasal	/m/		/n/							
Stop			/t/	/t ^s /			/k/			/ʔ/
	/b/		/d/	/d ^s /			/g/			
Fricative	/f/	/θ/	/s/	/s ^s /		/ʃ/	/ç/		/ħ/	/h/
		/ð/	/z/				/ʝ/		/ʕ/	
Affricatives					/ʒ/					
Approximant			/l/			/j/	/w/			
Trill			/r/							

4.1.2 HEBD Vowels

The minimal pair procedure is used here to decide how many vowels and diphthongs are used in HEBD. Each two vowels are said to be in contrast forming meaningful words to prove their existence in HEBD.

Table 4. 6: Minimal pair test of HEBD short vowels

Phoneme	Examples
/ʌ/ and /ɒ/	/rʌb/ ‘god’ /rɒb/ ‘a dress’
/a/ and /i/	/χal/ ‘vinegar’ /χil/ ‘a friend’
/ə/ and /u/	/bgə/ ‘he stayed’ bgu/ ‘they stayed’

Table 4. 7: Minimal pair test of HEBD long vowels

Phoneme	Examples
/i:/ and /ɔ:/	/s ^h i:t/ ‘fame’ /s ^h ɔ:t/ ‘a voice’
/ɑ:/ and /u:/	/gs ^h ɑ:r/ ‘shorts’ /gs ^h u:r/ ‘palaces’
// and /ɜ:/	/ha:m/ ‘important’ /hɜ:m/ ‘determined’

Table 4. 8: Minimal pair test of HEBD diphthongs

Phoneme	Examples

/ai/ and /a:/	/ʃaɪr/ ‘stones’ /ʃa:ɪ/ ‘shame’
/ei/ and /a:/	/neɪs/ ‘sand’ /na:s/ ‘people’

The minimal pair test reveals the existence of six short vowels (/ʌ/, /ɒ/, /ɑ/, /ɪ/, /ə/ and /u/), six long vowels (/i:/, /ɔ:/, /ɑ:/, /u:/, /a:/ and /ɜ:/) and two diphthongs (/ai/ and /ei/). The long vowel /a:/ is used in order for those two diphthongs form meaningful words when applying the minimal pair procedure.

4.2 Syllable Structure and Syllable Types

4.2.1 Syllable Structure

A syllable is a unit of speech made up of an onset and rhyme (Dawson and Phelan, 2016). The rhyme consists of a vowel, which is treated as the nucleus, plus any following consonant(s), described as the coda (Yule, 2010). Every syllable has a nucleus, which is usually a vowel (but can be a syllabic liquid or nasal) (Fromkin et al, 2014). The nucleus may be preceded and/or followed by one or more phonemes called the syllable onset and coda (Ibid). Thus, the universal structure for syllables is:

Figure 4.: 1 The Universal Structure of the Syllable, Yule (2010) and (Fromkin et al, 2014).

HEBD has fourteen syllable patterns ranging from the light syllable CV to the heaviest syllable CCVVC.

(a) CV	/na/	‘I’ final shif.ti
(b) CVC	/ʔam/	‘uncle’ final sal.lah
(c) CVV	/3ei/	‘he is coming’
(d) CVVC	/ʃein/	‘ugly’
(e) CVCC	/ʃams/	‘sun’
(f) CCV	/bkə	‘he cried’
(g) CCVC	/dfar/	‘he pushed’
(h) CCVV	/ɣnei/	‘my beloved’
(i)CCVCC	/ʔzəmt/	‘I decided’
(j) CVVCC	/sɜ:lm/	‘a proper name’
(k) CCVVC	/dɣeif/	‘loads ‘
(l) CCVVCC	/steibr/	‘he was greatful’
(m) CCCVV	/msti:.bər/	‘he is greatful’
(n) CCCVVC	/msti:b.rəh/	‘she is greatful’

Figure 4. 2: Figure 4.2: Syllable Patterns of HEBD

Al Tairi (2010) claimed that the syllable structure of MA like the Casablanca Moroccan dialect (Boudlal, 2001) is unique because there are complex onsets which are prohibited in CA and MSA, as well as most Arabic dialects. It is clear in the table above that the syllable structure of HEBD consists of complex onsets and complex codas which are prohibited in MA. CCVVCC does not take the long vowel /ɜ:/ as its VV

4.2.2 Syllable Types

Table 4. 9: Syllable Types in HEBD

Light		Heavy	
Initial	Final	Initial	Final
CV	CV	CVC	CVC
CCV		CVV	CVV
		CVCC	
		CCV	
		CCVC	CCVC
		CCVV	CCVV
		CCVCC	
		CCVVC	
		CCCVV	
		CCCVVC	

In HEBD, some syllable as CVVC, CVVCC and CCVVCC are restricted to free forms. CCV occurs initially. V is a short vowel. When an inflectional suffix is attached to CCV, the short vowel is modified to a long vowel or a diphthong as in the verb /ʔtʰə/ ‘he gave’. The schwa is replaced by the diphthong /ei/ when the suffix /tu/ is attached to it. The

realized form is /ʔt^saitu/ ‘you m.pl. gave’. The CCVV cluster does not take the diphthong /ei/ as its VV when it comes initially.

CHAPTER 5

Verb Measures of HEBD

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the HEBD verb Measures are discussed in details. It begins by providing an overview of the HEBD verbs as a preapprehension. Then, the researcher moves to discuss the verbs measures that are found in HEBD.

5.2. HEBD Verbs

As in many traditional descriptions of Semitic languages we can divide HEBD verbs into two classes depending on whether they are formed from a triliteral (three-consonant) or a quadriliteral (four-consonant) root. HEBD verbs consist of either two, three or four consonant roots. Those of two consonant roots fall under the geminated stems in which the second consonant is supposed to be geminated and form a trilateral stem as it is the case in SA. However, in HEBD no final consonant is allowed to be geminated. As a result, the roots remain bi-consonantal. For each lexical root, there are some derived stems. The bi-consonantal and tri-consonantal stems may fall in one of eight Measures out of the ten Measures of the Classical Arabic. The remaining two Measures which are the IV and the VIII, have no counterpart in HEBD. In his book “A Short Reference Grammar of Moroccan Arabic”, R. Harrell has adopted a model of ‘Measures’ to refer to the ten verb patterns of Standard Arabic (Farida, 2013). Since HEBD is an Arabic dialect, the verb Measures are described within the morphological framework of Arabic. Thus, the same model is used in this description. For every Sound (Regular) stem, a non-linear representation is provided.

5.3. Measure Patterns of the Trilateral Verb

In HEBD, there are eight patterns to which any bi-consonantal or tri-consonantal roots may fit in. Regarding SA, Holes (2004) claimed that the basic stem occurs in three vowel classes of the perfect base: [Faʕal], [Faʕila], [Faʕula]. HEBD trilateral verb patterns no longer follow this exact vowel system. The most common pattern is [fʕə/ for transitive and intransitive verbs. [fʕil/ is rarely used. As it has been said, the bi-consonantal roots are the HEBD version of the Classical Arabic trilateral geminated roots where the geminated radical does not get geminated when it is not followed by another radical.

5.3.1 Measure I Pattern

Three radicals form the stem of this measure. This form is considered to be the most productive one as most of the other forms are derived from. There are five different subcategories of this stem. Here is an explanation of how they are realized in HEBD.

5.3.1.1 Regular (Sound) Verb

The three radicals of this measure must be different. There are two surface forms of this measure. In the first form, the final vowel is /ə/, and in the second form, the final vowel is /i/. The following examples illustrate this morphological phenomenon:

Table 5. 1: Verbal inflection of regular (sound) stems of Measure I

Final Vowel /ə/		Final Vowel /i/	
نكر /nkər/	to deny	نكر /nkir/	to see
ربح /rbəħ/	to win	رجع /rʒiʕ/	to get back
لغخ /lfəχ/	to strik	نفع /nfiʕ/	to be useful
مخش /mχəʃ/	to add more	لشع /lʃiʕ/	to be stuck
دبغ /dbəɣ/	to beat	لغح /lgiħ/	to be pregnant (for animals)
سمع /sməʕ/	to hear	نقع /ngiʕ/	to soak

Figure 5. 1: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /kriħ/ Pattern

Figure 5. 2: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /lməʕ/ Pattern I

5.3.1.2 Geminate Verb

The underlying form of this measure is CVCCV where C2 is geminated. In HEBD V1 is not pronounced neither the final CV of this form. As a result, the surface form is CVC which makes it as bi-consonant stem.

- لف /laf/ → to turn
- صر /s^ʕar/ → to tie strictly
- فت /fat/ → to knead
- شم /ʃam/ → to sniff
- دف /daf/ → to push
- هاد/hɜ:d/ to fight

5.3.1.3 Hamzated Verb

One of the three consonants in this measure is hamzah. It may be the first, the second, or the third. When it comes initially, it gets elided. As a result, the second and the third consonants form the stem. In Standard Arabic, Abu-Chacra (2018) pointed out that the initial hamzah is elided in the imperative not in the perfect tense. Verbs that fall under this measure are limited in number.

- كل/kəl/ → to eat
- خد/χəd/ → to take

5.3.1.4 Hollow Verb

Hollow verbs are ones in which the second root consonant is actually a semiconsonant: either waaw or yaa (Ryding, 2005). These two semi-consonants undergo various mutations, turning into alif, a short vowel, or a long vowel depending on the word structure and derivation (Ibid). In HEBD, the vowel /a:/ form most of the stems of this type. If the final consonant is /t/, /f/, /d/ or /b/, then the vowel /ɜ:/ replaces the vowel /a/:

1) Examples with the vowel /a:/

- قال /ga:l/ → to say
- دار /da:r/ → to look for something or somebody
- داخ /da:χ/ → to faint
- زار /za:r/ → to visit

2) Examples with the vowel /ɜ:/

- شات /ʃɜ:t/ → to kick a ball
- شاف /ʃɜ:f/ → to see
- بات /bɜ:t/ → to spend the night
- فاد /fɜ:d/ → to be useful
- باد /bɜ:d/ → to exterminate
- ساب /sɜ:b/ → to leave behind
- تاب /tɜ:b/ → to repent

5.3.1.5 Defective Verb

Arabic dialects have a set of verbs which share a vowel-final stem (Watson, 2002). These verbs are traditionally known as third-weak or final-weak verbs (Ibid). Unlike the Standard Arabic, HEBD verbs which fall under this type take only one form which is taking the Schwa /ə/ as the vowel-final stem.

- بدأ /bdə/ → to begin
- بكى /bkə/ → to cry
- شكى /ʃkə/ → to complain

5.3.1.6 Assimilated Verb Roots

Ryding (2005) and Alfaifi (2016) pointed out that assimilated verb roots begin with a semi-consonant (waaw or yaa), most often (waaw). In HEBD, the stem vowel is one of two vowels: /ə/ or /i/. it precedes the third radical.

- وعد /wʔəd/ → to promise
- ولد /wlið/ → to give birth
- وصل /wsʔəl/ → to arrive

5.3.1.7 Doubly weak or “mixed” verb roots

Doubly weak verb roots have semi-consonants and a short vowel as the second and third radical. That should be enough to comprise the stem of this type with no further interdigitation of other vowels: only C1, as a consonant, C2, as a semi-consonant, and C3 as a short vowel.

- نوى /nwə/ → to intend
- كوى /kwə/ → to iron

- حوى /hwə/ → to catch fish using a net

5.3.2 Measure II Pattern

This measure is built on Measure I. It involves the lengthening of the second segment of some base root to express the intended morphological function. This germination characterizes the derivation of causative verbs.

5.3.2.1 Strong Sound and Strong Doubled Roots

In this pattern, there are three different consonants with a shadda on the second. The consonants that form the stem of this pattern must be sound once.

- لَزِمَ /lazzəṃ/ → to insist
- دَرَّبَ /darrəb/ → to train
- نَدَّرَ /naddər/ → to kick out
- رَضَخَ /radʿdʿəχ/ → to smash
- صَبَحَ /sʿabbəħ/ → to arrive in the morning
- غَدَّرَ /χaddər/ → to be late in the night

Figure 5. 3: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /sʿalliħ/ Pattern II

5.3.2.2 Middle Weak Roots (Hollow verbs)

One of the semi-consonants w or y takes the place of the second consonant and gets geminated. The first and the final consonants are sound once.

- رَوَّحَ /rawwəħ/ → to leave
- حَوَّطَ /ħawwətʕ/ → to circle somebody or something
- غَيَّرَ /ɣaiiər/ → to change
- رَيَّضَ /raiidʕ/ → to set something right

5.3.2.3 Geminate Verb

This type is derived from the Geminated stems of Measure I. The second and the third consonant are the same and the second one is doubled.

- عَمَّمَ /ʕəmməm/ → to dress somebody a turban
- عَدَّدَ /ʕaddəd/ → to enumerate
- هَلَّلَ /halləl/ → to be shocked

5.3.2.4 Hamzated Verbs

In Measure I, the hamaza is dropped when it comes initially. However, in this Measure, it is fully uttered.

- أَكَّدَ /ʔkkəd/ → 'to ensure'
- أَدَّبَ /ʔddəb/ → 'to discipline'

5.3.2.5 Defective Verbs

In HEBD, defective geminated stems end with a schwa. There are only two sound consonants of which the second is geminated.

- غَطَّى /ɣatˤtˤə/ → ‘to cover’
- طَفَّى /tˤaffə/ → ‘to turn off’
- لَصَّى /lasˤsˤə/ → ‘to turn on’

5.3.2.6 Assimilated Verb Roots

The semi-vowel /w/ occupies the place of C1. C2 which is the geminated one and C3 are sound consonants.

- وَكَّدَ /wəkkəd/ → to reserve a seat in a car
- وَرَدَ /warrəd/ → to import
- وَخَّرَ /waχχər/ → to move aside

5.3.3 Measure III Pattern

This measure is built on Measure I. A short vowel is inserted between the first and the second radicals. Some verbs which take this measure are derived from nouns.

- خَابَرَ /χabər/ → to greet somebody
- دَافَعَ /dafəʕ/ → to defend
- دَافَرَ /dɜ:fər/ → to push and be pushed
- تَاجَرَ /tɜ:jər/ → to trade

➤ تابع /tɜ:bəʕ/ → to follow

	r j ʕ	root	
CaCəC	. a . ə .	pattern	
	rajəʕ	form	‘to go over’

Figure 5. 4: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /rajəʕ/ Pattern III

5.3.4 Measure V Pattern

A reflexive version of Measure II. The prefix /t/, must be added. It begins with a cluster of two consonants; the prefix /t/ and another consonant. The first vowel is /a/ except for the defective verbs where the schwa /ə/ is used as the first vowel. For the geminated verbs the doubled radical is repeated after the final vowel.

5.3.4.1 Sound Verbs

➤ تَرَنَّقْ /trannəg/ → to get painted

➤ تَخَصَّمْ /tχasʕsʕəm/ → to tell jokes

➤ تَلَطَّمْ /tlatʕtʕəm/ → to be slapped repeatedly

	ʕ l m	root	
CCaCCəC	. . a . . ə .	pattern	
	tʕalləm	form	‘to learn’

Figure 5. 5: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /tʕalləm/ Pattern V

5.3.4.2 Geminate Verbs

- تخصص /tχas^ss^sʕs^s/ → to be specialized
- نخطط /tχat^tt^tət^t/ → to be

5.3.4.3 Hollow Verbs

- تنوّر /tnawwər/ → to be brighter
- تَوَسَّخ /twassəχ/ → to be dirty
- تَوَرَّط /twarret^t/ → to be embroiled

5.3.4.4 Defective Verbs

- تعبى /tʔəbba/ → to be loaded
- تملأ /tməlla/ → to be filled

5.3.5 Measure VI Pattern

This measure is derived mostly from measure I and III. It takes the prefix /t/ as its first radical. . Usually a reflexive measure.

5.3.5.1 Derived from Measure III

This type of measure VI is the most regular one. All the stems take either the long vowel /ɜ:/ or the diphthong /ei/. When the stems of the measure take the long vowel /ɜ:/, the schwa is inserted before the last radical to break the CCVVCC syllable which does not take the long vowel /ɜ:/ as its VV.

- تقاصد /tgɜ:sʕəd/ → ‘to compete in poems’
- تقابل /tgɜ:bəl/ → ‘to meet’
- تفاهم /tfɜ:həm/ → ‘to get understanding with somebody’
- تخيزل /tχeizl/ → ‘to make fun of someone’
- تشيطن /tʃeitʕn/ → ‘to be evil’

Figure 5. 6: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /ts^ʕɜ:mər/ Pattern VI

4.3.5.2 Derived from Measure I

Only two types of measure I fall under this measure. There is a distinctive Pattern for every type.

1) *Geminate Verbs*

- خَبَّ /χəb/ to run → تخاب /tχa:b/ to run with others
- مَدَّ /məd/ to stretch out parts of the body → تماد /tmə:d/ to shake hands
- عَضَّ /ʕədʕ/ to bite → تعاض /tʕa:dʕ/ to bite and be bitten

2) *Defective Verb*

- نَسِيَ /nsə/ to forget → تناسى /tnə:sə/ to pretend forgetting
- شَكَى /ʃkə/ to complain → تشاكى /tʃə:kə/ to complain to a magisterial figure
- بَكَى /bkə/ to cry → تباكى /tbə:kə/ to cry alongside others

5.3.6. Measure VII Pattern

Built on measure I by adding the prefix /ʔn/. Usually a reflexive and/or passive version of measure I. This measure is used in HEBD for verbs that can not take /t/ after the first radical as the verbs that come under Measure VIII do. It would be difficult to pronounce. Verb stems of this measure are limited in number. The schwa is inserted to break up the cluster, because HEBD does not allow a cluster of more than three consonants.

- اندرم /ʔəndrəm/ → to be hurt (of wounded part of the body)
- انطحن /ʔəntʰən/ → to be pulverized
- انزعج /ʔənzəj/ → to be disturbed
- اندفش /ʔəndfəʃ/ → to be beaten

z ʕ j root

CəCCCəC . ə . . . ə . pattern

ʔənzʕəj form 'to be disturbed'

Figure 5. 7: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /ʔənzʕəj/ Pattern VII

5.3.6.1 Derived from Measure I Geminaed Verbs

/d^ʕar/ 'to harm' → انضر/ʔnd^ʕar/ 'to be harmed'

/d^ʕam/ 'to conjoin' → انضم/ʔnd^ʕam/ 'to join'

/ʃag/ 'to tear apart' → انشق/ʔnʃag/ 'to split'

5.3.7 Measure VIII Pattern

Derived from measure I. The morpheme [t] is inserted between the first and the second radicals. It is one of few measures where a vowel is placed after C1. Often a reflexive or passive version of Measure I. There is a distinctive form for every type of measure I that comes under this measure.

Table 5. 2: An inflectional paradigm of type patterns of Measure VIII

The type	Measure I pattern	Derived measure VIII pattern
Sound verbs	حفر /ħfər/ to dig	حتفر /ħitfər/ to be digged
	فغص /fɣəs ^ʕ / to squeeze	فتغص /fitɣəs ^ʕ / to be squeezed
	قعم /gʕəm/ to rip off	قتعم /gitʕəm/ to get ripped off
Geminate verbs	عد /ʕad/ to count	عتد /ʕtəd/ to be counted
	كب /kab/ to pour	كتب /ktəb/ to be poured
	كر /kar/ to hit something	كتر /ktər/ to be hit
Hollow verbs	خان /χa:n/ to betray	ختان /χtɜ:n/ to be betrayed

	شاف /ʃɜ:f/ to see خان /ha:n/ to offend	شتاف /ʃtɜ:f/ to be seen هتان /htɜ:n/ to be insulted
Defective	رشى /ərʃə/ to bribe شفا /ʃfə/ to heal خبا /χbə/ to hide somebody or something	/ritʃə/ to be bribed /ʃitfə/ to be healed /χittbə/ to hide yourself
Mixed verbs	روى /rwə/ to quench لوى /lwə/ to twist عوى /ʕwə/ to get obstinacy	/ritwə/ to be quenched /litwə/ to be twisted /ʕitwə/ to get obstinacy
Assimilated	وهم وقف وصل	/ʔttəhəm/ /ʔttəfəg/ /ʔttəsʕəl/

Badawi, Carter and Gully (2016) claimed that the phonology of measure VIII is complicated by the fact that the infix -t- assimilates to the first radical of the verb in various ways. The examples below from HEBD illustrate this morphological phenomenon:

1) Partial assimilation, progressive /t/ > /tʕ/

- صطف /sʕitʕfətʕ/ to be distracted
- صطاب /sʕitʕləb/ to be capable
- صطقع /sʕitʕgəʕ/ to become deaf

2) Complete assimilation, progressive /t/ > /tʕ/, /t/ > /d/, /t/ > /sʕ/

- قَطَّع /gitʕtʕəʕ/ to be cut
- هَدَّمَ /hiddəmm/ to be demolish
- عَصَّبَ /ʕisʕsʕəb/ to align with your family

3) Automatic assimilation, doubled /t/

- فتش /ftəħ/ to open → فتش /fittəħ/ ‘to be opened’
- قتل /gtəl/ to kill → قتل /gittəl/ ‘to be killed’
- فتن /ftən/ to turn s.b against s.b → فتن /fitən/ ‘to be turned against someone else’

m y s^ʕ root
 CiCCəC . i . . ə . pattern
 mityəs^ʕ form ‘to be enraged’

Figure 5. 8: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /fityəs^ʕ/ Pattern VIII

5.3.8 Measure X Pattern

This measure begins with the biconsonantal cluster /st/. Most of the stems of this measure are derived from Measure I. Few are derived from nouns.

5.3.8.1 Sound Verbs

- ستهيل /stəhbəl/ → to kid
- ستعمل /stəʕməl/ → to use

ħ m l root

CCaCCəC . . a . . ə . pattern
 stahməl form ‘to endure’

Figure 5. 9: Non-Linear Representation of HEBD Verb /stahməl/ Pattern X

5.3.8.2 Geminated Verbs

/ʔstmər/ ‘to continue’

/ʔstfəd/ ‘to be ready’

/ʔstfəz/ ‘to provok’

5.3.8.3 Hollow Verbs

/ʔstfɜ:d/ ‘to benefit’

/ʔstgɜ:m/ ‘to stand

/ʔstræh/ ‘to take rest’

/ʔstfæd/ ‘to take back’

5.3.8.4 Assimilated Verbs

➤ ستاكل /stɜ:kl/ → to be eroded/to be eaten

➤ ستامن /stɜ:mn/ → to rely on

- ستيبر /steibr/ → to be gateful
- ستيح /steidh/ → to walk by the sea

5.3 Quadrilateral Verbs

There must be four consonants to form quadrilateral verbs. Sometimes the four consonants are all different and sometimes they are reduplicated (Ryding, 2005). The stem that those consonants form must not be derived of any pattern of trilateral verb patterns. Wightwick and Gaatar (2008) and Abu-Chacra (2018) claimed that in SA, quadrilateral verbs are conjugated as Measure II فَعَّلَ faʿʿala (i.e. CaCCaCa) of the regular trilateral verb. According to Ryding (2005) this is possible because the trilateral Measure II is increased by one consonant by virtue of the doubling of its second radical. Although HEBD verbs do not always conjugate the same way as SA verbs do, these two measures still conjugate the same. The following examples give an explanation of HEBD quadrilateral verb patterns.

5.3.1 Regular Quadrilaterals

- عنكل /ʕankəl/ → to obstruct somebody with your leg
- طربغ /tʕarbəy/ → to splash about in a pool
- طنبل /tʕanbəl/ → to get upset
- خريش /χarbəʃ/ → to make a quiet sound
- رنقش /rangəʃ/ → to decorate

5.3.2 Reduplicated Quadrilateral

- كركر /karkər/ → to kick s,body/s.thing repeatedly

- فكفك /fakfək/ → to open something into pieces
- فقتفت /fatfət/ → to crush something into small pieces
- دردر /dardər/ → to hang out
- مطمط /mat^ʕmət^ʕ/ → to stretch several times

5.3.3 Quadrilateral derived verbs

The prefix /t/ is added to quadrilateral verbs. The derived measure is considered to be a reflexive or passive of quadrilateral verbs.

- تبهدل /tbahdəl/ → to be deformed
- تنرفز /tnarfəz/ → to be annoyed
- تعنطز /tʕant^ʕəz/ → to be arrogant
- تكلوس /tkalwəs/ → to be wrapped up in a blanket
- تمردهغ /tmardəy/ → to be over beaten

CHAPTER 6

VERBAL INFLECIION

6.1 Introduction

HEBD verbs inflect for gender, number and person. It is as Al-Huneety (2015) put it a verb inflects for gender, number and person to ensure subject-verb agreement. This sort of

verbal inflection is achieved by means of affixation. The system of affixation in HEBD is indeed a complicated phenomenon. One affix carries out information about gender, number and person. Those affixes are attached to the stem. In addition, sometimes there is a vocalic change. Which means some stems are altered in order to get inflected. The problem is that sometimes there are more than one affixes for the same person, gender and number depending on the different patterns.

6.2 The Perfect Aspect

In the perfect aspect, verbs are attached to affixes in order to inflect. All the inflectional affixes that are used are suffixes. As mentioned before, each suffix carries out information about gender, number and person. First person is gender-neutral. The 1.s. and the 2.m.s take the same suffix. The difference is determined by the context. The 3.m.s. takes no suffix and considered to be the infinitive form. According to Danks (2011) Arabic grammarians refer to this paradigm verb as *faʕala* “to do” to illustrate inflectional morphology. The inflectional suffixes of the perfect aspect in HEBD are presented in the following table.

Table 6. 1: The inflectional suffixes of the perfect aspect in HEBD

Person-Gender	Number	
	s	Pl
1	-t	-nə
2m	-t	-tu
2f	-ti	-tən

3m		-u
3f	-ət	-ən

When the suffixes of the 1s, 1pl, 2m.s, 2m.pl, 2f.s and 2f.pl are attached to the perfective stems of any measure except the stems of Measure I trilateral sound, trilateral hamzated and trilateral assimilated and of measure VII, they demand the diphthong /ei/ to be added before them. That means this diphthong will be added at the end of the perfective stems. It replaces the vowels that come at the end of some measures such as the defective and the mixed verbs of measure I. In HEBD, the diphthong /ei/ marks the perfect aspect for the patterns that take it. The hollow verbs of measure I do not take this diphthong. However, they get their vowel replaced by the vowels /u/ or /i/ when a perfective suffix is added.

For the third person, there are three vowel-initial subject suffixes /u/, /ət/ and /ən/ which are added to 3m.pl, 3f.s, and 3f.pl respectively. The schwa /ə/ that comes at the end of the defective verbal stems and mixed verbal stems gets replaced by 3f.s and 3m.pl vowel-initial subject suffixes /ən/. The 3f.pl perfective suffix take the diphthong /ei/ when it is attached to a defective verbal stem or a mixed verbal stem. the vowel . 3m.s. is considered to be the form upon which the other forms are built. The following examples give extra clarification to this matter.

Table 6. 2: Examples of the third person perfective suffixes

	Sound	Mixed	Defective
3.m.s	/ɣləb/ ‘he refused’	/t ^s wə/ ‘he folded’	/dmə/ ‘he bled’

3.f.s	/ɣlɔbət/ ‘she refused’	/t ^s wət/ ‘she folded’	/dmət/ ‘she bled’
3.m.pl	/ɣlɔbu/ ‘they (m. pl.) refused’	/t ^s wu/ ‘they (m. pl.) folded’	/dmu/ ‘they (m. pl.) bled’
3.f.pl	/ɣlɔbən/ ‘they (f. pl.) refused’	/t ^s wein/ ‘they (f. pl.) folded’	/dmein/ ‘they (f. pl.) bled’

6.2.1 Trilateral verbs

6.2.1.1 Sound Verbs

The inflection of the trilateral sound verbs varies from one measure to another. Measure I Pattern is considered to be one of few measures where the verbal inflection of sound verbs is concatenative. The perfective suffixes and the perfective sound stems are linearly concatenated. The following table provide an example of the verbal inflection of one of the sound verbs of Measure I Pattern.

Table 6. 3: The inflectional paradigm of the form I verb /ɣmɔz/ ‘to wink’

/ɣmɔz/ ‘to wink’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ɣmɔzt/	I winked
1. p	/ɣmɔznə/	we winked
2. m. s	/ɣmɔzt/	you (m. s.) winked
2. m. pl.	/ɣmɔztu/	you (m. pl.) winked

2. f. s.	/χmæzti/	you (f. s.) winked
2. f. pl	/χmæztin/	you (f. pl.) winked
3. m. s.	/χmæz/	he winked
3. m. pl	/χmæzu/	they (m. pl.) winked
3. f. s.	/χmæzət/	she winked
3. f. pl.	/χmæzən/	they (f. pl.) winked

Sound Verbs (II-X)

Most of the sound derived verbs take the diphthong /ei/ as they inflect for the 1st.sg. and pl, 2m.s, 2m.pl, 2f.s and 2f.p. The insertion of this diphthong marks the verbal inflection of the perfect aspect. Measure VII and Measure VIII do not take the diphthong /ei/. As a result, the perfective suffixes are attached without causing any internal change to the perfective stems. In measure II, III, V and VI, the schwa that is inserted before the final radical of the 3m.s to break the CCVVCC syllable is omitted when the inflectional suffixes are attached to the stems of those measures. In measure VII, VIII and X the schwa is omitted when the inflectional suffixes of 3m.pl, 3f.s and 3f.pl are attached to the stems of the previous measures and preserved with the rest of the inflectional suffixes. The following tables provide examples of the verbal inflection of the sound verbs of the derived Measure in HEBD.

Table 6. 4: The inflectional paradigm for the Form II verb /s^ʕabbən/ ‘to wash’

/s ^ʕ abbən/ ‘to wash’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/s ^ʕ abbneit/	I washed
1. p	/s ^ʕ abbneinə/	we washed
2. m. s	/s ^ʕ abbneit/	you (m. s.) washed
2. m. pl.	/s ^ʕ abbneitu/	you (m. pl.) washed

2. f. s.	/s ^ʃ abbneiti/	you (f. s.) washed
2. f. pl	/s ^ʃ abbneitin/	you (f. pl.) washed
3. m. s.	/s ^ʃ abbən/	he washed
3. m. pl	/s ^ʃ abbnu/	they (m. pl.) washed
3. f. s.	/s ^ʃ abbnət/	she washed
3. f. pl.	/s ^ʃ abbnən/	they (f. pl.) washed

Table 6. 5: The inflectional paradigm for the form III verb /tɜ:bəʃ/ ‘to follow’

/tɜ:bəʃ/ ‘to follow’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/tɜ:bʃeit/	I followed
1. p	/tɜ:bʃeinə/	we followed
2. m. s	/tɜ:bʃeit/	you (m. s.) followed
2. m. pl.	/tɜ:bʃeitu/	you (m. pl.) followed
2. f. s.	/tɜ:bʃeiti/	you (f. s.) followed
2. f. pl	/tɜ:bʃeitin/	you (f. pl.) followed
3. m. s.	/tɜ:bəʃ/	he followed
3. m. pl	/tɜ:bʃu/	they (m. pl.) followed
3. f. s.	/tɜ:bʃət/	she followed
3. f. pl.	/tɜ:bʃən/	they (f. pl.) followed

Table 6. 6: The inflectional paradigm for the Form V verb /tʃəlləm/ ‘to learn’

/tʃəlləm/ ‘to learn’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/tʃəllmeit/	I learned
1. p	/tʃəllmeinə/	we learned
2. m. s	/tʃəllmeit/	you (m. s.) learned
2. m. pl.	/tʃəllmeitu/	you (m. pl.) learned
2. f. s.	/tʃəllmeiti/	you (f. s.) learned
2. f. pl	/tʃəllmeitin/	you (f. pl.) learned

3. m. s.	/tʃəlləm/	he learned
3. m. pl	/tʃəllmu/	they (m. pl.) learned
3. f. s.	/tʃəllmət/	she learned
3. f. pl.	/tʃəllmən/	they (f. pl.) learned

Table 6. 7: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VI verb /tʃɜ:səm/ ‘to share’

/tʃɜ:səm/ ‘to share’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/tʃɜ:smeɪt/	I shared
1. p	/tʃɜ:smeɪnə/	we shared
2. m. s	/tʃɜ:smeɪt/	you (m. s.) shared
2. m. pl.	/tʃɜ:smeɪtu/	you (m. pl.) shared
2. f. s.	/tʃɜ:smeɪti/	you (f. s.) shared
2. f. pl	/tʃɜ:smeɪtɪn/	you (f. pl.) shared
3. m. s.	/tʃɜ:səm/	he shared
3. m. pl	/tʃɜ:smu/	they (m. pl.) shared
3. f. s.	/tʃɜ:smit/	she shared
3. f. pl.	/tʃɜ:smin/	they (f. pl.) shared

Table 6. 8: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VII verb /ʔəns^ʃdəm/ ‘to be shocked’

/ʔəns ^ʃ dəm/ ‘to be shocked’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔəns ^ʃ dəmt/	I was shocked
1. p	/ʔəns ^ʃ dəmnə/	we were shocked
2. m. s	/ʔəns ^ʃ dəmt/	you (m. s.) were shocked
2. m. pl.	/ʔəns ^ʃ dəmtu/	you (m. pl.) were shocked
2. f. s.	/ʔəns ^ʃ dəmti/	you (f. s.) were shocked
2. f. pl	/ʔəns ^ʃ dəmtɪn/	you (f. pl.) were shocked

3. m. s.	/ʔəns ^ɕ dəm/	he was shocked
3. m. pl	/ʔəns ^ɕ dmu/	they (m. pl.) were shocked
3. f. s.	/ʔəns ^ɕ dmit/	she was shocked
3. f. pl.	/ʔəns ^ɕ dmin/	they (f. pl.) were shocked

Table 6. 9: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /gitbəs^ɕ/ ‘to be stung’

/gitbəs ^ɕ / ‘to be stung’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/gitbəs ^ɕ t/	I was stung
1. p	/gitbəs ^ɕ nə/	we were stung
2. m. s	/gitbəs ^ɕ t/	you (m. s.) were stung
2. m. pl.	/gitbəs ^ɕ tu/	you (m. pl.) were stung
2. f. s.	/gitbəs ^ɕ ti/	you (f. s.) were stung
2. f. pl	/gitbəs ^ɕ tin/	you (f. pl.) were stung
3. m. s.	/gitbəs ^ɕ /	he was stung
3. m. pl	/gitbs ^ɕ u/	they (m.) were stung
3. f. s.	/gitbs ^ɕ it/	she was stung
3. f. pl.	/gitbs ^ɕ in/	they (f.) were stung

Table 6. 10: The inflectional paradigm for the Form X verb /stəχdəm/ ‘to use’

/stəχdəm/ ‘to use’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/stəχdəmeit/	I used
1. p	/stəχdəmeinə/	we used
2. m. s	/stəχdəmeit/	you (m. s.) used
2. m. pl.	/stəχdəmeitu/	you (m. pl.) used
2. f. s.	/stəχdəmeiti/	you (f. s.) used

2. f. pl	/stəχdəmeitin/	you (f. pl.) used
3. m. s.	/stəχdəm/	he used
3. m. pl	/stəχdmu/	they (m.) used
36. f. s.	/stəχdmit/	she used
3. f. pl.	/stəχdmin/	they (f.) used

6.2.1.2 Geminate Verbs

As it has been discussed before, in HEBD, the second radical of the geminate verbs of Measure I does not get geminated as it does in Arabic language. In HEBD, when the perfective suffixes are attached to it, it gets geminated. When a geminated radical of any Measure in HEBD is the last radical of a stem, it does not get geminated unless a perfective suffix is attached to it. That is not the case for the 3m.s because it takes no suffix. This appearance of the geminated radicals is accompanied by the addition of the diphthong /ei/ and perfective suffixes for the 1 and 2 and perfective suffixes alone for the 3 except for the 3m.s. which remains free of suffixes.

Table 6. 11: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʕəd^ʕ/ ‘to bite’

/ʕəd ^ʕ / ‘to bite’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʕəd ^ʕ d ^ʕ eit/	I bite
1. p	/ʕəd ^ʕ d ^ʕ einə/	We bite
2. m. s	/ʕəd ^ʕ d ^ʕ eit/	you (m. s.) bite
2. m. pl.	/ʕəd ^ʕ d ^ʕ eitu/	you (m. pl.) bite
2. f. s.	/ʕəd ^ʕ d ^ʕ eiti/	you (f. s.) bite
2. f. pl	/ʕəd ^ʕ d ^ʕ eitin/	you (f. pl.) bite

3. m. s.	/ʒədʰ/	he bites
3. m. pl	/ʒədʰdʰu/	they (m.) bite
3. f. s.	/ʒədʰdʰit/	she bites
3. f. pl.	/ʒədʰdʰin/	they (f.) bite

Table 6. 12: The inflectional paradigm for the Form II verb /səddəd/ ‘to pay’

/səddəd/ ‘to pay’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/səddədeit/	I paid
1. p	/səddədeinə/	we paid
2. m. s	/səddədeit/	you (m. s.) paid
2. m. pl.	/səddədeitu/	you (m. pl.) paid
2. f. s.	/səddədeiti/	you (f. s.) paid
2. f. pl	/səddədeitin/	you (f. pl.) paid
3. m. s.	/səddəd/	he paid
3. m. pl	/səddədu/	they (m.) paid
3. f. s.	/səddəditi/	she paid
3. f. pl.	/səddəditi/	they (f.) paid

Table 6. 13: The inflectional paradigm for the Form V verb /tsəmməm/ ‘to be poisoned’

/tsəmməm/ ‘to be poisoned’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/tsəmməmeit/	I was poisoned
1. p	/tsəmməmeinə/	we were poisoned
2. m. s	/tsəmməmeit/	you (m. s.) were poisoned
2. m. pl.	/tsəmməmeitu/	you (f. pl.) were poisoned
2. f. s.	/tsəmməmeiti/	you (f. s.) were poisoned
2. f. pl	/tsəmməmeitin/	you (f. pl.) were poisoned

3. m. s.	/tsəmməm/	he was poisoned
3. m. pl	/tsəmməmu/	they (f.) were poisoned
3. f. s.	/tsəmməmit/	she was poisoned
3. f. pl.	/tsəmməmin/	they (f.) were poisoned

Table 6. 14: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VI verb /tsɜ:d/ ‘to reconcile

/tsɜ:d/ ‘to reconcile ’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/tsɜ:ddeit/	I reconciled
1. p	/tsɜ:ddeinə/	we reconciled
2. m. s	/tsɜ:ddeit/	you (m. s.) reconciled
2. m. pl.	/tsɜ:ddeitu/	you (f. pl.) reconciled
2. f. s.	/tsɜ:ddeiti/	you (f. s.) reconciled
2. f. pl	/tsɜ:ddeitin/	you (f. pl.) reconciled
3. m. s.	/tsɜ:d/	he reconciled
3. m. pl	/tsɜ:du/	they (f.) reconciled
3. f. s.	/tsɜ:dit/	she reconciled
3. f. pl.	/tsɜ:din/	they (f.) reconciled

Table 6. 15: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VII verb /ʔəndəg/ ‘to be beaten’

/ʔəndəg/ ‘to be beaten’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔəndəggeit/	I was beaten
1. p	/ʔəndəggeinə/	we were beaten
2. m. s	/ʔəndəggeit/	you (m. s.) were beaten
2. m. pl.	/ʔəndəggeitu/	you (f. pl.) were beaten
2. f. s.	/ʔəndəggeiti/	you (f. s.) were beaten
2. f. pl	/ʔəndəggeitin/	you (f. pl.) were beaten

3. m. s.	/ʔəndəg/	he was beaten
3. m. pl	/ʔəndəggu/	they (f.) were beaten
3. f. s.	/ʔəndəggit/	she was beaten
3. f. pl.	/ʔəndəggin/	they (f.) were beaten

Table 6. 16: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /χtəf/ ‘to become insane’

/χtəf/ ‘to become insane’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/χtəffei/	I became insane
1. p	/χtəffeinə/	we became insane
2. m. s	/χtəffei/	you (m. s.) became insane
2. m. pl.	/χtəffei/	you (m. pl.) became insane
2. f. s.	/χtəffei/	you (f. s.) became insane
2. f. pl	/χtəffei/	you (f. pl.) became insane
3. m. s.	/χtəf/	he became insane
3. m. pl	/χtəffu/	they (m.) became insane
3. f. s.	/χtəffit/	she became insane
3. f. pl.	/χtəffin/	they (f.) became insane

Table 6. 17: The inflectional paradigm for the Form X verb /ʔstgər/ ‘to settle in’

/ʔstgər/ ‘to settle in’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔstgərreit/	I settled in
1. p	/ʔstgərreinə/	we settled in
2. m. s	/ʔstgərreit/	you (m. s.) settled in
2. m. pl.	/ʔstgərreitu/	you (m. pl.) settled in
2. f. s.	/ʔstgərreiti/	you (f. s.) settled in
2. f. pl	/ʔstgərreitin/	you (f. pl.) settled in

3. m. s.	/ʔstgər/	he settled in
3. m. pl	/ʔstgərru/	they (m.) settled in
3. f. s.	/ʔstgərrit/	she settled in
3. f. pl.	/ʔstgərrin/	they (f.) settled in

6.2.1.3 Hamzated Verbs

Hamzated verbs are few in HEBD. They inflect for number, gender and person by attaching the perfective suffixes to the perfective Hamzated stems. The following tables illustrate the verbal inflection of two Hamzated verbs one of Measure I and another one of Measure II. The perfective suffixes attached to the stems of Measure I cause no internal change and those attached to the stems Measure II alter those stems.

Table 6. 18: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /kəl/ ‘to eat’

/kəl/ ‘to eat’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/kəlt/	I ate
1. p	/kəlnə/	We ate
2. m. s	/kəlt/	you (m. s.) ate
2. m. pl.	/kəltu/	you (m. pl.) ate
2. f. s.	/kəlti/	you (f. s.) ate
2. f. pl	/kəltin/	you (f. pl.) ate

3. m. s.	/kəl/	he ate
3. m. pl	/kəlu/	they (m.) ate
3. f. s.	/kəlit/	she ate
3. f. pl.	/kəlin/	they (f.) ate

Table 6. 19: The inflectional paradigm for the Form II verb /ʔkkəd/ ‘to ensure’

/ʔkkəd/ ‘to ensure’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔkkədeit/	I ensured
1. p	/ʔkkədeinə/	we ensured
2. m. s	/ʔkkədeit/	you (m. s.) ensured
2. m. pl.	/ʔkkədeitu/	you (m. pl.) ensured
2. f. s.	/ʔkkədeiti/	you (f. s.) ensured
2. f. pl	/ʔkkədeitin	you (f. pl.) ensured
3. m. s.	/ʔkkəd/	he ensured
3. m. pl	/ʔkkədu/	they (m.) ensured
3. f. s.	/ʔkkədit	she ensured
3. f. pl.	/ʔkkədin	they (f.) ensured

6.2.1.4 Hollow Verbs

In HEBD, hollow verbs come under four measures. Each one of those measures inflect differently. Hollow verbs of measure I get their vowel replaced by the vowel /u/ as they inflect for the 1 and 2. For the 3, the perfective suffixes are attached to the original vowel. The case of the hollow verbs of measure VI is similar to the majority of the verbs in HEBD where the diphthong /ei/ is inserted before the perfective suffixes. This insertion happens, as it has been mentioned before, when the perfective stems are inflected for the 1 and 2. The

vowel of the hollow verbs of Measure VIII is replaced by the short vowel /i/ as they inflect for the 1 and 2. The inflection of Hollow verbs of measure X is a concatenative one. The following tables provide examples of the inflection of the hollow verbs in HEBD.

Table 6. 20: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /za:r/ ‘to visit’

/za:r/ ‘to visit’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/zurt/	I visited
1. p	/zurnə/	We visited
2. m. s	/zurt/	you (m. s.) visited
2. m. pl.	/zurtu/	you (m. pl.) visited
2. f. s.	/zurti/	you (f. s.) visited
2. f. pl	/zurtin/	you (f. pl.) visited
3. m. s.	/za:r/	he visited
3. m. pl	/za:ru/	they (m.) visited
3. f. s.	/za:rit/	she visited
3. f. pl.	/za:rin/	they (f.) visited

Table 6. 21: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VI verb /tʰəiəɾ/ ‘to pour’

/tʰəiəɾ/ ‘to pour’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/tʰəiəreit/	I poured
1. p	/tʰəiəreinə/	we poured
2. m. s	/tʰəiəreit/	you (m. s.) poured
2. m. pl.	/tʰəiəreitu/	you (m. pl.) poured
2. f. s.	/tʰəiəreiti/	you (f. s.) poured
2. f. pl	/tʰəiəreitin/	you (f. pl.) poured
3. m. s.	/tʰəiəɾ/	he poured

3. m. pl	/t ^s əiəru/	they (m.) poured
3. f. s.	/t ^s əiərit/	she poured
3. f. pl.	/t ^s əiərin/	they (f.) poured

Table 6. 22: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /htɜ:n/ ‘to be insulted’

/htɜ:n/ ‘to be insulted’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/htint/	I was insulted
1. p	/htinnə/	we were insulted
2. m. s	/htint/	you (m. s.) were insulted
2. m. pl.	/htintu/	you (m. pl.) were insulted
2. f. s.	/htinti/	you (f. s.) was insulted
2. f. pl	/htinən/	you (f. pl.) were insulted
3. m. s.	/htɜ:n/	he was insulted
3. m. pl	/htɜ:nu/	they (m.) were insulted
3. f. s.	/htɜ:nət/	she was insulted
3. f. pl.	/htɜ:nən/	they (f.) were insulted

Table 6. 23: The inflectional paradigm for the Form X verb /ʔstd^sæf/ ‘to host’

/ʔstd ^s æf/ ‘to host’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔəstd ^s æft/	I hosted
1. p	/ʔəstd ^s æfnə/	We hosted
2. m. s	/ʔəstd ^s æft/	you (m. s.) hosted
2. m. pl.	/ʔəstd ^s æfu/	you (m. pl.) hosted
2. f. s.	/ʔəstd ^s æfti/	you (f. s.) hosted
2. f. pl	/ʔəstd ^s æftən/	you (f. pl.) hosted
3. m. s.	/ʔəstd ^s æf/	he hosted

3. m. pl	/ʔəstɔ̃ ^s æf/	they (m.) hosted
3. f. s.	/ʔəstɔ̃ ^s æfət/	she hosted
3. f. pl.	/ʔəstɔ̃ ^s æfən/	they (f.) hosted

6.2.1.5 Defective verbs

All the defective verbs that are found in HEBD end with a schwa. It is considered to be the final vowel. As those verbs inflect in HEBD, this schwa gets omitted. The processes of omitting the schwa is the same in all the different measures under which the defective verbs come. When the defective verbs of measure I inflect for the 1 and the 2, the diphthong /ei/ replaces the schwa. The perfective suffixes of the 3 are vowel initial suffixes. As a result, when the defective verbs inflect for the 3, no vowel is inserted except for the 3f.pl. where the vowel of the perfective suffixes is /ei/ instead of /i/. The following tables provide examples of the inflection of the defective verbs from every measure they come under.

Table 6. 24: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /bkə/ ‘to cry’

/bkə/ ‘to cry’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/bkeit/	I cried
1. p	/bkeinə/	We cried
2. m. s	/bkeit/	you (m. s.) cried
2. m. pl.	/bkeitu/	you (m. pl.) cried
2. f. s.	/bkeitɪ/	you (f. s.) cried
2. f. pl	/bkeitən/	you (f. pl.) cried
3. m. s.	/bkə/	he cried

3. m. pl	/bku/	they (m.) cried
3. f. s.	/bkət/	she cried
3. f. pl.	/bkən/	they (f.) cried

Table 6. 25: The inflectional paradigm for the Form II verb /dəllə/ ‘to show’

/dəllə/ ‘to show’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/dəlleit/	I showed
1. p	/dəlleinə/	We showed
2. m. s	/dəlleit/	you (m. s.) showed
2. m. pl.	/dəlleitu/	you (m. pl.) showed
2. f. s.	/dəlleiti/	you (f. s.) showed
2. f. pl	/dəlleitən/	you (f. pl.) showed
3. m. s.	/dəllə/	He showed
3. m. pl	/dəllu/	they (m.) showed
3. f. s.	/dəllət/	She showed
3. f. pl.	/dəllein/	they (f.) showed

Table 6. 26: The inflectional paradigm for the Form V verb /trəbbə/ ‘to be raised’

/trəbbə/ ‘to be raised’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/trəbbeit/	I was raised
1. p	trəbbeinə/	we were raised
2. m. s	trəbbeit/	you (m. s.) were raised
2. m. pl.	trəbbeitu/	you (m. pl.) were raised
2. f. s.	trəbbeiti/	you (f. s.) were raised
2. f. pl	trəbbeitin/	you (f. pl.) were raised

3. m. s.	/trəbbə/	he was raised
3. m. pl	/trəbbu/	they (m.) were raised
3. f. s.	/trəbbit/	she was raised
3. f. pl.	/trəbbin/	they (f.) were raised

Table 6. 27: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /kitfə/ ‘to have enough’

/kitfə/ ‘to have enough’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/kitfeit/	I had enough
1. p	/kitfeinə/	we had enough
2. m. s	/kitfeit/	you (m. s.) had enough
2. m. pl.	/kitfeitu/	you (m. pl.) had enough
2. f. s.	/kitfeiti/	you (f. s.) had enough
2. f. pl	/kitfeitin/	you (f. pl.) had enough
3. m. s.	kitfə/	he had enough
3. m. pl	/kitfu/	they (m.) had enough
3. f. s.	/kitfit	she had enough
3. f. pl.	/kitfin/	they (f.) had enough

6.2.1.6 Assimilated Verbs

The inflection of the assimilated verbs depend on wheather there is a /w/ in the perfective stem or not. All the perfective stems that have /w/ as one of their radicals take the diphthong /ei/ when they inflect for the 1 and the 2. in measure VIII the /w/ gets assimilated and turned into /t/. Assimilated verbs of Measure VIII do not take the diphthong /ei/. Examples of different assimilated verbs and their measures are found in the following tables.

Table 6. 28: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ws^ʕəf/ ‘to describe’

/ws ^ɕ əf/ ‘to describe’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ws ^ɕ əft/	I described
1. p	/ws ^ɕ əfnə/	We described
2. m. s	/ws ^ɕ əft/	you (m. s.) described
2. m. pl.	/ws ^ɕ əftu/	you (m. pl.) described
2. f. s.	/ws ^ɕ əfti/	you (f. s.) described
2. f. pl	/ws ^ɕ əftin/	you (f. pl.) described
3. m. s.	/ws ^ɕ əf/	he described
3. m. pl	/ws ^ɕ əfu/	they (m. pl.) described
3. f. s.	/ws ^ɕ əfit/	she described
3. f. pl.	/ws ^ɕ əfin/	they (f. pl.) described

Table 6. 29: The inflectional paradigm for the Form II verb /wəs^ɕs^ɕəl/ ‘to deliver’

/wəs ^ɕ s ^ɕ əl/ ‘to deliver’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/wəs ^ɕ s ^ɕ əleit/	I delivered
1. p	/wəs ^ɕ s ^ɕ əlnə/	we delivered
2. m. s	/wəs ^ɕ s ^ɕ əleit/	you (m. s.) delivered
2. m. pl.	/wəs ^ɕ s ^ɕ əleitu/	you (m. pl.) delivered
2. f. s.	/wəs ^ɕ s ^ɕ əleiti/	you (f. s.) delivered
2. f. pl	/wəs ^ɕ s ^ɕ əleitin/	you (f. pl.) delivered
3. m. s.	/wəs ^ɕ s ^ɕ əl/	he delivered

3. m. pl	/wəs ^s s ^s əlu/	they (m.) delivered
3. f. s.	/wəs ^s s ^s əlɪt/	she delivered
3. f. pl.	/wəs ^s s ^s əlin/	they (f.) delivered

Table 6. 30: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /ʔttəfəg/ ‘to agree’

/ʔttəfəg/ ‘to agree’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔttəfəgt/	I agreed
1. p	/ʔttəfəgnə/	we agreed
2. m. s	/ʔttəfəgt/	you (m. s.) agreed
2. m. pl.	/ʔttəfəgtu/	you (m. pl.) agreed
2. f. s.	/ʔttəfəgti/	you (f. s.) agreed
2. f. pl	/ʔttəfəgtin/	you (f. pl.) agreed
3. m. s.	/ʔttəfəg/	he agreed
3. m. pl	/ʔttəfəgu/	they (m.) agreed
3. f. s.	/ʔttəfəgit/	she agreed
3. f. pl.	/ʔttəfəgin/	they (f.) agreed

/stwʁəb/ ‘to realize’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/stwʁəbeit/	I realized
1. p	/stwʁəbeitnə/	we realized
2. m. s	/stwʁəbeit/	you (m. s.) realized
2. m. pl.	/stwʁəbeitu/	you (m. pl.) realized
2. f. s.	/stwʁəbeiti/	you (f. s.) realized
2. f. pl	/stwʁəbeitin/	you (f. pl.) realized
3. m. s.	/stwʁəb/	he realized

3. m. pl	/stwʒəbu/	they (m.) realized
3. f. s.	/stwʒəbit/	she realized
3. f. pl.	/stwʒəbin/	they (f.) realized

Table 6. 31: The inflectional paradigm for the Form X verb /stwʒəb/ ‘to realize’

6.2.1.7 Mixed Verbs

Mixed verbs come only under measure I and Measure VIII. They have both the semi-vowel /w/ and the schwa as their final radicals. When the perfective suffixes are attached to those verbs, as they inflect for the 1 and 2, the schwa is replaced by the diphthong /ei/. When the defective verbs inflect for the 3, no vowel is inserted except for the 3f.pl where the vowel of the perfective suffixes is /ei/ instead of /i/.

Table 6. 32: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /gwə/ ‘to have appetite’

/gwə/ ‘to have appetite’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/gweit/	I had appetite
1. p	/gweinə/	We had appetite
2. m. s	/gweit/	you (m. s.) had appetite
2. m. pl.	/gweitu/	you (m. pl.) had appetite
2. f. s.	/gweiti/	you (f. s.) had appetite
2. f. pl	/gweitin/	you (f. pl.) had appetite
3. m. s.	/gwə/	he had appetite

3. m. pl	/gwu/	they (m.) had appetite
3. f. s.	/gwit/	she had appetite
3. f. pl.	/gwein/	they (f.) had appetite

Table 6. 33: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /kitwə/ ‘to be ironed’

/kitwə/ ‘to be ironed’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/kitweit/	I was ironed
1. p	/kitweinə/	we were ironed
2. m. s	/kitweit/	you (m. s.) were ironed
2. m. pl.	/kitweitu/	you (m. pl.) were ironed
2. f. s.	/kitweiti/	you (f. s.) were ironed
2. f. pl	/kitweitin/	you (f. pl.) were ironed
3. m. s.	/kitwə/	he was ironed
3. m. pl	/kitwu/	they (m.) were ironed
3. f. s.	/kitwit/	she was ironed
3. f. pl.	/kitwein/	they (f.) were ironed

6.2.2 Quadrilateral verbs

The regular quadrilateral and the reduplicated quadrilateral stems consist of four radicals and the derived quadrilateral stems consist of five radicals. Two syllables form these measures. The schwa is used as the nucleus of the second syllable. It gets replaced by the diphthong/ei/ when imperfective stems are inflected for the 1s & pl, and m & f. and the 2 s. & pl., and m. & f. When perfective stems are inflected the 3m.pl. the schwa is elided as the suffix /u/ is attached to the stem.

Table 6. 34: The inflectional paradigm for the regular quadrilateral verb /zambəl/ ‘he shows off

/zambəl/ ‘to have appetite’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/zambleit/	I skived off
1. p	/zambleinə/	We skived off
2. m. s	/zambleit/	you (m. s.) skived off
2. m. pl.	/zambleitu/	you (m. pl.) skived off
2. f. s.	/zambleiti/	you (f. s.) skived off
2. f. pl	/zambleitin/	you (f. pl.) skived off
3. m. s.	/zambəl/	he skived off
3. m. pl	/zambu/	they (m.) skived off
3. f. s.	/zablət/	she skived off
3. f. pl.	/zablən/	they (f.) skived off

Table 6. 35: The inflectional paradigm for the reduplicated quadrilateral verb /ɣaryər/ ‘to be almost drown ’

/ɣaryər/ ‘to be almost drown ’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/ɣaryreit/	I almost drown
1. p	/ɣaryreinə/	We almost drown
2. m. s	/ɣaryreit/	you (m. s.) almost drown
2. m. pl.	/ɣaryreitu/	you (m. pl.) almost drown
2. f. s.	/ɣaryreiti/	you (f. s.) almost drown
2. f. pl	/ɣaryreitin/	you (f. pl.) almost drown
3. m. s.	/ɣaryər/	he almost drown
3. m. pl	/ɣaryru/	they (m.) almost drown
3. f. s.	/ɣaryrət/	she almost drown

3. f. pl.	/ɣaryrən/	they (f.) almost drown
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Table 6. 36: The inflectional paradigm for quadrilateral derived verb /tɣarʃəʃ/ ‘to shatter’

/tɣarʃəʃ/ ‘to shatter’	Perfect	Gloss
1. s	/tɣarʃeɪt/	I shattered
1. p	/tɣarʃeɪnə/	We shattered
2. m. s	/tɣarʃeɪt/	you (m. s.) shattered
2. m. pl.	/tɣarʃeɪtu/	you (m. pl.) shattered
2. f. s.	/tɣarʃeɪti/	you (f. s.) shattered
2. f. pl	/tɣarʃeɪtin/	you (f. pl.) shattered
3. m. s.	/tɣarʃəʃ/	he shattered
3. m. pl	/tɣarʃu/	they (m.) shattered
3. f. s.	/tɣarʃət/	she shattered
3. f. pl.	/tɣarʃən/	they (f.) shattered

6.3 Imperfective Aspect

In the imperfect aspect, there are different affixes used to get verbs inflected. An explanation of the imperfect affixes is provided below.

1) 1s. & pl. and m. & f. Afixes

1 is number-neutral and gender-neutral. That means one affix is used to indicate the gender and number of 1. The prefix /n/ is used to indicate 1. If the stems have /n/, /m/ /r/ /l/ or /w/ as their first radical, then assimilation occurs and that radical gets doubled. For the stems of the trilateral hamzated verbs and of measure VII the prefix /nə/ is used instead of /ʔən/.

➤ /frəħ/.....’became happy’ → /ʔənrəħ/ ‘I/we get happy’

worth to mention that, in the imperfect aspect, verbs of Measure I have different stem vowels. That means, sound verbs are realized with different stem vowels in the imperfect aspect so are the geminate, and hollow verbs. An illustration of the different stem vowels of Measure I verbs is provided with examples in the following table.

Table 6. 38: The stem vowel of the imperfective Sound, Geminate and Hollows stems of Measure I

The Pattern	The Perfect Stems	The Imperfect Stems
Trilateral Sound	/dʁəl/ ‘he entered’	/ʔidʁul/ ‘he entered’
Trilateral Sound	/fdʰəħ/ ‘he exposed’	/ʔifdʰəħ/ ‘he exposes’
Trilateral Geminate	/sʰətʰ/ ‘he became silence’	/ʔisʰutʰ/ ‘he becomes silence’
Trilateral Geminate	/ʃəd/ ‘he tightened’	/ʔiʃid/ ‘he tightens’
Trilateral Geminate	/zəl/ ‘he erred’	/ʔizəl/ ‘he errs’
Trilateral Hollow	/sʰa:ħ/ ‘he shouted’	/ʔisʰiəħ/ ‘he shouts’
Trilateral Hollow	/da:r/ ‘he moved around’	/ʔidwər/ ‘he moves around’
Trilateral Hollow	/fɜ:d/ ‘he became useful’	/ʔifi:d/ ‘he becomes useful’

Hamazated verbs, defective verbs and mixed verbs have only one stem vowel for each which are provided in following table.

Table 6. 39: The stem vowel of the imperfective Hamzated, Defective and Mixed stems of Measure I

The Pattern	Perfective Stem	Imperfective Stem
Trilateral Hamzated	/ʁəd/ ‘he ate’	/ʔiʁud/ ‘he buys’
Trilateral Defective	/bkə/ ‘he cried’	/ʔibki/ ‘he cries’
Trilateral mixed	/dʰwə/ ‘he arrived at night’	/ʔidʰwi/ ‘he arrives at night’

The other trilateral patterns and the quadrilaterals have the same vowels of the perfect. Only the prefix /ʔi/ is added to the perfective stems to change them into imperfective once. This prefix is added to 3m.s and pl imperfective stems. 3m.s works as the counterpart of 3m.s perfective. It is replaced by other prefixes as long as the other categories concerned.

6.3.1 Trilateral Verbs

The verbal inflection of the imperfect trilateral verbs varies from one Measure to another. Measure I is considered to be the most complicated one. As it has been mentioned, different stem vowels are used with the same pattern.

6.3.1.1 Sound Verbs

The schwa /ə/ appears in the stems of Measure III, V, VI, VII, VIII and X as the stem vowel. The stem vowel of Measure II is /i/ and either /u/ or /ə/ for Measure I. The prefix /t/ is not used for the Measure V and VI because they have /t/ as their first radical. More clarification is provided in the following tables.

/ʔi-s ^ʕ rut ^ʕ / ‘he swallows’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-s ^ʕ rut ^ʕ /	I swallow
1. p	/ʔən-s ^ʕ rut ^ʕ /	we swallow
2. m. s	/tə-s ^ʕ rut ^ʕ /	you (m.s.) swallow
2. m. pl.	/tə-s ^ʕ rut ^ʕ -u/	you (m.pl.) swallow
2. f. s.	/tə-s ^ʕ rut ^ʕ -i/	you (f.s.) swallow
2. f. pl	/tə-s ^ʕ rut ^ʕ -ən/	you (f.pl.) swallow

3. m. s.	/ʔi-sʰrutʰ/	he swallows
3. m. pl	/ʔi-sʰrutʰ-u/	they (m.) swallow
3. f. s.	/tə-sʰrutʰ/	she swallows
3. f. pl.	/tə-sʰrutʰ-ən/	they (f.) swallow

Table 6. 40: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-sʰrutʰ/ ‘he swallows’

Table 6. 41: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-mʃəʃ/ ‘he scares’

/ʔi-mʃəʃ/ ‘he scares’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔəm-mʃəʃ/	I scare
1. p	/ʔəm-mʃəʃ/	we scare
2. m. s	/tə-mʃəʃ/	you (m.s.) scare
2. m. pl.	/tə-mʃəʃ-u/	you (m.pl.) scare
2. f. s.	/tə-mʃəʃ-i/	you (f.s.) scare
2. f. pl	/tə-mʃəʃ-ən/	you (f.pl.) scare
3. m. s.	/ʔi-mʃəʃ/	he scares
3. m. pl	/ʔi-mʃəʃ-u/	they (m.) scare
3. f. s.	/tə-mʃəʃ/	she scares
3. f. pl.	/tə-mʃəʃ-ən/	they (f.) scare

/ʔi-rənnəg/ ‘he paints’	Imperfect	Gloss
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1. s	/ʔər- rənnəg/	I paint
1. p	/ʔər- rənnəg/	we paint
2. m. s	/t- rənnəg/	you (m.s.) paint
2. m. pl.	/t- rənnəg-u/	you (m.pl.) paint
2. f. s.	/t- rənnəg-i/	you (f.s.) paint
2. f. pl	/t- rənnəg-ən/	you (f.pl.) paint
3. m. s.	/ʔi- rənnəg/	he paints
3. m. pl	/ʔi- rənnəg-u/	they (m.) paint
3. f. s.	/t- rənnəg/	she paints
3. f. pl.	/t- rənnəg-ən/	they (f.) paint

Table 6. 42: The inflectional paradigm for the Form II verb /ʔi-rənnəg/ ‘he paints’

Table 6. 43: The inflectional paradigm for the Form III verb /ʔi-s3:fər/ ‘he travels’

/ʔi-s3:fər/ ‘he travels’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-s3:fər/	I travel
1. p	/ʔən-s3:fər/	we travel
2. m. s	/t-s3:fər/	you (m.s.) travel
2. m. pl.	/t-s3:fər-u/	you (m.pl.) travel
2. f. s.	/t-s3:fər-i/	you (f.s.) travel
2. f. pl	/t-s3:fər-ən/	you (f.pl.) travel
3. m. s.	/ʔi-s3:fər/	he travels
3. m. pl	/ʔi-s3:fər-u/	they (m.) travel
3. f. s.	/t-s3:fər/	she travels
3. f. pl.	/t-s3:fər-ən/	they (f.) travel

Table 6. 44: The inflectional paradigm for the Form V verb /ʔi-tχabər/ ‘he scares’

/ʔi-tχabər/ ‘he asks’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-tχabər/	I ask
1. p	/ʔən-tχabər/	we ask
2. m. s	/-tχabər/	you (m.s.) ask
2. m. pl.	/-tχabər-u/	you (m.pl.) ask
2. f. s.	/-tχabər-i/	you (f.s.) ask
2. f. pl	/-tχabər-ən/	you (f.pl.) ask
3. m. s.	/ʔi-tχabər/	he asks
3. m. pl	/ʔi-tχabər-u/	they (m.) ask
3. f. s.	/-tχabər/	she asks
3. f. pl.	/-tχabər-ən/	they (f.) ask

Table 6. 45: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VI verb /ʔi-tgɜ:bəl/ ‘he meets’

/ʔi-tgɜ:bəl/ ‘he meets’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-tgɜ:bəl /	I meet
1. p	/ʔən-tgɜ:bəl/	we meet
2. m. s	/-tgɜ:bəl/	you (m.s.) meet
2. m. pl.	/-tgɜ:bəl-u/	you (m.pl.) meet
2. f. s.	/-tgɜ:bəl-i/	you (f.s.) meet
2. f. pl	/-tgɜ:bəl-ən/	you (f.pl.) meet
3. m. s.	/ʔi-tgɜ:bəl/	he meets
3. m. pl	/ʔi-tgɜ:bəl-u/	they (m.) meet
3. f. s.	/-tgɜ:bəl/	she meets
3. f. pl.	/-tgɜ:bəl-ən/	they (f.) meet

/ʔi-nzʂəj/ ‘he is disturbed’	Imperfect	Gloss
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1. s	/nə-ʔənzʃəj/	I am disturbed
1. p	/nə-ʔənzʃəj/	we are disturbed
2. m. s	/t-ʔənzʃəj/	you (m.s.) are disturbed
2. m. pl.	/t-ʔənzʃəj-u/	you (m.pl.) are disturbed
2. f. s.	/t-ʔənzʃəj-i/	you (f.s.) are disturbed
2. f. pl	/t-ʔənzʃəj-ən/	you (f.pl.) disturbed
3. m. s.	/ʔi-nzʃəj/	he is disturbed
3. m. pl	/ʔi-nzʃəj-u/	they (m.) are disturbed
3. f. s.	/t-ʔənzʃəj/	she is disturbed
3. f. pl.	/t-ʔənzʃəj-ən/	they (f.) are disturbed

Table 6. 46: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VII verb /ʔi-nzʃəj/ ‘he is disturbed’

Table 6. 47: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /ʔi-rtʃəb/ ‘he is terrified’

/ʔi-rtʃəb/ ‘he is terrified’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔər-rtʃəb/	I am terrified
1. p	/ʔər-rtʃəb/	we are terrified
2. m. s	/tə-rtʃəb/	you (m.s.) are terrified
2. m. pl.	/tə-rtʃəb-u/	you (m.pl.) are terrified
2. f. s.	/tə-rtʃəb-i/	you (f.s.) are terrified
2. f. pl	/tə-rtʃəb-ən/	you (f.pl.) are terrified
3. m. s.	/ʔi-rtʃəb/	he is terrified
3. m. pl	/ʔi-rtʃəb-u/	they (m.) are terrified
3. f. s.	/tə-rtʃəb/	she is terrified
3. f. pl.	/tə-rtʃəb-ən/	they (f.) are terrified

Table 6. 48: The inflectional paradigm for the Form X verb /ʔi-stəhbəl/ ‘he slides’

/ʔi-stəhbəl/ ‘he slides’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-stəhbəl/	I slide
1. p	/ʔən-stəhbəl/	we slide
2. m. s	/tə-stəhbəl/	you (m.s.) slide
2. m. pl.	/tə-stəhbəl-u/	you (m.pl.) slide
2. f. s.	/tə-stəhbəl-i/	you (f.s.) slide
2. f. pl	/tə-stəhbəl-ən/	you (f.pl.) slide
3. m. s.	/ʔi-stəhbəl/	he slides
3. m. pl	/ʔi-stəhbəl-u/	they (m.) slide
3. f. s.	/tə-stəhbəl/	she slides
3. f. pl.	/tə-stəhbəl-ən/	they (f.) slide

6.3.1.2 Geminated

In HEBD, a geminated radical does not get geminated unless it is followed by another radical. No final radical gets geminated in HEBD. The geminated stems of Pattern I takes one of three vowels /i/, /u/ or /ə/ as its stem vowel. The stem of Pattern X get *st* as the first radicals. When it is inflected, a short vowel /i/ is inserted to break the cluster.

Table 6. 49: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-kuf/ ‘he slaps’

/ʔi-kuf/ ‘he slaps’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-kuf/	I slap
1. p	/ʔən-kuf/	we slap
2. m. s	/t-kuf/	you (m.s.) slap
2. m. pl.	/t-kuff-u/	you (m.pl.) slap
2. f. s.	/t-kuff-i/	you (f.s.) slap

2. f. pl	/t-kuff-ən/	you (f.pl.) slap
3. m. s.	/ʔi-kuf/	he slaps
3. m. pl	/ʔi-kuff-u/	they (m.) slap
3. f. s.	/t-kuf/	she slaps
3. f. pl.	/t-kuff-ən/	they (f.) slap

Table 6. 50: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-sid/ ‘he blocks’

/ʔi-sid/ ‘he blocks’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-sid/	I block
1. p	/ʔən-sid/	we block
2. m. s	/t-sid/	you (m.s.) block
2. m. pl.	/t-sidd-u/	you (m.pl.) block
2. f. s.	/t-sidd-i/	you (f.s.) block
2. f. pl	/t-sidd-ən/	you (f.pl.) block
3. m. s.	/ʔi-sid/	he blocks
3. m. pl	/ʔi-sidd-u/	they (m.) block
3. f. s.	/t-sid/	she blocks
3. f. pl.	/t-sidd-ən/	they (f.) block

Table 6. 51: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-həm/ ‘he intends’

/ʔi-həm/ ‘he intend ’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-həm/	I intend
1. p	/ʔən-həm/	we intend
2. m. s	/t-həm/	you (m.s.) intend
2. m. pl.	/t-həmm-u/	you (m.pl.) intend
2. f. s.	/t-həmm-i/	you (f.s.) intend
2. f. pl	/t-həmm-ən/	you (f.pl.) intend
3. m. s.	/ʔi-həm/	he intends
3. m. pl	/ʔi-həmm-u/	they (m.) intend
3. f. s.	/t-həm/	she intends
3. f. pl.	/t-həmm-ən/	they (f.) intend

Table 6. 52: The inflectional paradigm for the Form II verb /ʔi-rəmməm/ ‘he scares’

/ʔi-rəmməm/ ‘he reconstructs’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔər-rəmməm/	I reconstruct
1. p	/ʔər-rəmməm/	we reconstruct
2. m. s	/t-rəmməm/	you (m.s.) reconstruct
2. m. pl.	/t-rəmməm-u/	you (m.pl.) reconstruct
2. f. s.	/t-rəmməm-i/	you (f.s.) reconstruct
2. f. pl	/t-rəmməm-ən/	you (f.pl.) reconstruct
3. m. s.	/ʔi-rəmməm/	he reconstructs
3. m. pl	/ʔi-rəmməm-u/	they (m.) reconstruct
3. f. s.	/t-rəmməm/	she reconstructs
3. f. pl.	/t-rəmməm-ən/	they (f.) reconstruct

Table 6. 53: The inflectional paradigm for the Form V verb /tməddəd/ ‘he lays’

/ʔi- tməddəd/ ‘he lays’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-tməddəd/	I lay
1. p	/ʔən-tməddəd/	we lay
2. m. s	/t-tməddəd/	you (m.s.) lay
2. m. pl.	/t-tməddəd-u/	you (m.pl.) lay
2. f. s.	/t-tməddəd-i/	you (f.s.) lay
2. f. pl	/t-tməddəd-ən/	you (f.pl.) lay
3. m. s.	/ʔi-tməddəd/	he lays
3. m. pl	/ʔi-tməddəd-u/	they (m.) lay
3. f. s.	/-tməddəd/	she lays
3. f. pl.	/-tməddəd-ən/	they (f.) lay

Table 6. 54: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VI verb /ʔi-thɜ:d/ ‘he fights’

/ʔi- thɜ:d/ ‘he fights’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-thɜ:d/	I fight
1. p	/ʔən-thɜ:d/	we fight
2. m. s	/tə-thɜ:d/	you (m.s.) fight
2. m. pl.	/tə-thɜ:dd-u/	you (m.pl.) fight
2. f. s.	/tə-thɜ:dd-i/	you (f.s.) fight
2. f. pl	/tə-thɜ:d-ən/	you (f.pl.) fight
3. m. s.	/ʔi-thɜ:d/	he fights
3. m. pl	/ʔi-thɜ:d-u/	they (m.) fight
3. f. s.	/tə-thɜ:d/	she fights
3. f. pl.	/tə-thɜ:d-in/	they (f.) fight

Table 6. 55: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VII verb /ʔi-nddɛf/ ‘he gets pushed’

/ʔi-nddǎf/ ‘he gets pushed’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔǎn-ndǎf/	I get pushed
1. p	/ʔǎn-ndǎf/	we get pushed
2. m. s	/tǎ-ndǎf/	you (m.s.) get pushed
2. m. pl.	/tǎ-ndǎff-u/	you (m.pl.) get pushed
2. f. s.	/tǎ-ndǎff-i/	you (f.s.) get pushed
2. f. pl.	/tǎ-ndǎff-ǎn/	you (f.pl.) get pushed
3. m. s.	/ʔi-ndǎf/	he gets pushed
3. m. pl.	/ʔi-ndǎff-u/	they (m.) get pushed
3. f. s.	/tǎ-ndǎf/	she gets pushed
3. f. pl.	/tǎ-ndǎff-ǎn/	they (f.) get pushed

Table 6. 56: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /ʔi-rtǎf/ ‘he have a bath’

/ʔi-rtǎf/ ‘he has a bath’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔǎn-rtǎf/	I have a bath
1. p	/ʔǎn-rtǎf/	we have a bath
2. m. s	/tǎ-rtǎf/	you (m.s.) have a bath
2. m. pl.	/tǎ-rtǎff-u/	you (m.pl.) have a bath
2. f. s.	/tǎ-rtǎff-i/	you (f.s.) have a bath
2. f. pl.	/tǎ-rtǎff-ǎn/	you (f.pl.) have a bath
3. m. s.	/ʔi-rtǎf/	he has a bath
3. m. pl.	/ʔi-rtǎff-u/	they (m.) have a bath
3. f. s.	/tǎ-rtǎf/	she has a bath
3. f. pl.	/tǎ-rtǎff-ǎn/	they (f.) have a bath

Table 6. 57: The inflectional paradigm for the Form X verb /ʔi-strǎd/ ‘he takes back’

/ʔi-strəd/ 'he takes back'	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-ʔstrəd/	I take back
1. p	/ʔən-ʔstrəd/	we take back
2. m. s	/tə-ʔstrəd/	you (m.s.) take back
2. m. pl.	/tə-ʔstrədd-u/	you (m.pl.) take back
2. f. s.	/tə-ʔstrəd-i/	you (f.s.) take back
2. f. pl	/tə-ʔstrəd-ən/	you (f.pl.) take back
3. m. s.	/ʔi-ʔstrəd/	he takes back
3. m. pl	/ʔi-ʔstrəd-u/	they (m.) take back
3. f. s.	/tə-ʔstrəd/	she takes back
3. f. pl.	/tə-ʔstrəd-ən/	they (f.) take back

6.3.1.3 Hamzated Verbs

In HEBD, the Hamzated verbs that inflect in the imperfective aspect are limited in number. When they inflect in the imperfect, the stem vowel is changed from the schwa in the perfect into /u/ in the imperfect. Here is an example in the following table of the inflection of the hollow imperfective stem /ʔi-kul/ 'he eats'.

/ʔi-kul/ 'he eats'	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-kul/	I eat
1. p	/ʔən-kul/	we eat
2. m. s	/t-kul/	you (m.s.) eat
2. m. pl.	/t-kul-u/	you (m.pl.) eat
2. f. s.	/t-kul-i/	you (f.s.) eat

2. f. pl	/t-kul-ən/	you (f.pl.) eat
3. m. s.	/ʔi-kul/	he eats
3. m. pl	/ʔi-kul-u/	they (m.) eat
3. f. s.	/t-kul/	she eats
3.f.pl.	/t-kul-ən/	they (f.) eat

Table 6. 58: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-kul/ ‘he eats’

6.3.1.4 Hollow verbs

The hollow verbs of Measure I take one of the two long vowels /u:/ or /ɜ:/ as their stem vowel. Those of Measure III and V get no internal change. Only the imperfective affixes are added to change the perfective stems into imperfect ones without any internal change. In Table 6:60, the perfective stem begins with /t^s/ which get complete assimilation with the imperfective prefix /t/. as it has been already noted, this process of assimilation demand the morpheme /ʔə/ to be added initially.

Table 6. 59: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-mu:t/ ‘he dies’

/ʔi-mu:t/ ‘he dies’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔəm-mu:t/	I die
1. p	/ʔəm-mu:t/	we die
2. m. s	/t-mu:t/	you (m.s.) die
2. m. pl.	/t-mu:t-u/	you (m.pl.) die
2. f. s.	/t-mu:t-i/	you (f.s.) die
2. f. pl	/t-mu:t-ən/	you (f.pl.) die
3. m. s.	/ʔi-mu:t/	he dies
3. m. pl	/ʔi-mu:t-u/	they (m.) die
3. f. s.	/t-mu:t/	she dies
3. f. pl.	/t-mu:t-ən/	they (f.) die

Table 6. 60: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-tʰz:ħ/ ‘he walk in sleep’

/ʔi-tʰz:ħ/ ‘he walks in sleep’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-tʰz:ħ/	I walk in sleep
1. p	/ʔən-tʰz:ħ/	we walk in sleep
2. m. s	/ʔətʰ-tʰz:ħ/	you (m.s.) walk in sleep
2. m. pl.	/ʔətʰ-tʰz:ħ-u/	you (m.pl.) walk in sleep
2. f. s.	/ʔətʰ-tʰz:ħ-i/	you (f.s.) walk in sleep
2. f. pl	/ʔətʰ-tʰz:ħ-ən/	you (f.pl.) walk in sleep
3. m. s.	/ʔi-tʰz:ħ/	he walks in sleep
3. m. pl	/ʔi-tʰz:ħ-u/	they (m.) walk in sleep
3. f. s.	/ʔətʰ-tʰz:ħ/	she walks in sleep
3. f. pl.	/ʔətʰ-tʰz:ħ-ən/	they (f.) walk in sleep

Table 6. 61: The inflectional paradigm for the Form III verb /ʔi-dawəm/ ‘he attends’

/ʔi-dawəm/ ‘he attends’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-dawəm/	I attend
1. p	/ʔən-dawəm/	we attend
2. m. s	/t-dawəm/	you (m.s.) attend
2. m. pl.	/t-dawəm-u/	you (m.pl.) attend
2. f. s.	/t-dawəm-i/	you (f.s.) attend
2. f. pl	/t-dawəm-ən/	you (f.pl.) attend
3. m. s.	/ʔi-dawəm/	he attends
3. m. pl	/ʔi-dawəm-u/	they (m.) attend
3. f. s.	/t-dawəm/	she attends
3. f. pl.	/t-dawəm-ən/	they (f.) attend

Table 6. 62: The inflectional paradigm for the Form V verb /ʔi-tχai:iər/ ‘he chooses’

/ʔi-tχai:iər/ ‘he chooses’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-tχai:iər/	I choose
1. p	/ʔən-tχai:iər/	we choose
2. m. s	/tə-tχai:iər/	you (m.s.) choose
2. m. pl.	/tə-tχai:iər-u/	you (m.pl.) choose
2. f. s.	/tə-tχai:iər-i/	you (f.s.) choose
2. f. pl	/tə-tχai:iər-ən/	you (f.pl.) choose
3. m. s.	/ʔi-tχai:iər/	he chooses
3. m. pl	/ʔi-tχai:iər-u/	they (m.) choose
3. f. s.	/tə-tχai:iər/	she chooses
3. f. pl.	/tə-s ^ʕ i:ħ-ən/	they (f.) choose

6.3.1.5 Defective Verbs

The schwa of the defective verbs in the perfect aspect is turned into the short vowel /i/ when those verbs get inflected in the imperfect aspect. This /i/ gets elided when it is followed by a vowel-initial suffixes. When the followed suffix is a consonant-initial, a pause takes place on C2 and the /i/ is moved towards the consonant-initial suffix. The following examples provide more clarification.

Table 6. 63: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-ʕt^ʕi/ ‘he gives’

/ʔi-ʕt ^ʕ i/ ‘he gives’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-ʕt ^ʕ i/	I give
1. p	/ʔən-ʕt ^ʕ i/	we give
2. m. s	/tə-ʕt ^ʕ i/	you (m.s.) give

2. m. pl.	/tə-ŋt ^s -u/	you (m.pl.) give
2. f. s.	/tə-ŋt ^s i/	you (f.s.) give
2. f. pl	/tə-ŋt ^s -ən/	you (f.pl.) give
3. m. s.	/ʔi-ŋt ^s i/	he gives
3. m. pl	/ʔi-ŋt ^s -u/	they (m.) give
3. f. s.	/tə-ŋt ^s i/	she gives
3. f. pl.	/tə-ŋt ^s -ən/	they (f.) give

Table 6. 64: The inflectional paradigm for the Form II verb /ʔi-fd^sd^si/ ‘he empties’

/ʔi-fd ^s d ^s i/ ‘he empties’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-fəd ^s d ^s i/	I empties
1. p	/ʔən-fəd ^s d ^s i/	we empties
2. m. s	/t-fəd ^s d ^s i/	you (m.s.) empties
2. m. pl.	/t-fəd ^s d ^s -u/	you (m.pl.) empties
2. f. s.	/t-fəd ^s d ^s i/	you (f.s.) empties
2. f. pl	/t-fəd ^s d ^s -ən/	you (f.pl.) empties
3. m. s.	/ʔi-fəd ^s d ^s i/	he empties
3. m. pl	/ʔi-fəd ^s d ^s -u/	they (m.) empties
3. f. s.	/t-fəd ^s d ^s -ən/	she empties

/ʔi-lɜ:gi/ ‘he meets’	Imperfect 100	Gloss
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1. s	/ʔəl-lɜ:gi/	I meet
1. p	/ʔəl-lɜ:gi/	we meet
2. m. s	/t-lɜ:gi/	you (m.s.) meet
2. m. pl.	/t-lɜ:g-u/	you (m.pl.) meet
2. f. s.	/t-lɜ:gi/	you (f.s.) meet
2. f. pl	/t-lɜ:g-in/	you (f.pl.) meet
3. m. s.	/ʔi-lɜ:gi/	he meets
3. m. pl	/ʔi-lɜ:g-u/	they (m.) meet
3. f. s.	/t-lɜ:gi/	she meets

Table 6. 65: The inflectional paradigm for the Form III verb /ʔi-lɜ:gi/ ‘he meets’

6.3.1.6 Assimilated Verbs

Only the assimilated stems of Measure I and VIII are found in HEBD. Assimilated verbs of Measure 1 take the vowel /i/ as their stem vowel when they are inflected in the imperfective. However, it is not the case in the perfective aspect where the vowel /a/ appears to be the stem vowel of the assimilated verbs. Here is an example of the transforming of a verb from the perfective into the imperfective:

- ✓ /wlad/ ‘gave birth’
- ✓ /ʔi-wlid/ ‘gives birth’

The prefix /ʔi/ is added along with the internal change where /i/ takes the place of /a/ in the imperfective. The following tables provide examples of the inflectional paradigms of the imperfective stems of pattern I and VIII.

Table 6. 66: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-wlid/ ‘he gives birth’

/ʔi-wlid/ ‘he gives birth’	Imperfect	Gloss
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1. s	/ʔəw-wlid/	I give birth
1. p	/ʔəw-wlid/	we give birth
2. m. s	/tə-wlid/	you (m.s.) give birth
2. m. pl.	/tə-wlid-u/	you (m.pl.) give birth
2. f. s.	/tə-wlid-i/	you (f.s.) give birth
2. f. pl	/tə-wlid-n/	you (f.pl.) give birth
3. m. s.	/ʔi-wlid/	he gives birth
3. m. pl	/ʔi-wlid-u/	they (m.) give birth
3. f. s.	/tə-wlid/	she gives birth
3. f. pl.	/tə-wlid-n/	they (f.) give birth

Table 6. 67 The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /ʔi-ʔttəs^ʕəl/ ‘he calls’

/ʔi-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl/ ‘he call’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl /	I call
1. p	/ʔən-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl/	we call
2. m. s	/tə-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl /	you (m.s.) call
2. m. pl.	/tə-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl-u/	you (m.pl.) call
2. f. s.	/tə-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl-i/	you (f.s.) call
2. f. pl	/tə-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl-n/	you (f.pl.) call
3. m. s.	/ʔi-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl/	he calls
3. m. pl	/ʔi-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl-u/	they (m.) call
3. f. s.	/tə-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl/	she calls
3. f. pl.	/tə-ʔttəs ^ʕ əl-n/	they (f.) call

6.3.1.7 Mixed Verbs

Mixed stems of Measure I and VIII are inflected in HEBD. as it has already been said, the prefix /ʔi/ must be added before the 3rd imperfective stem of all measures. For the mixed stems of Measure I and VIII, also the final vowel is replaced by another vowel in the imperfect. The final vowel of Measure I and VIII verbs is /ə/ in the imperfective aspect and /i/ in the imperfective aspect. The following tables provide more clarification to this matter.

Table 6. 68: The inflectional paradigm for the Form I verb /ʔi-nwi/ ‘he intends’

/ʔi-nwi/ ‘he intends’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-nwi/	I intend
1. p	/ʔən-nwi/	we intend
2. m. s	/t ə-nwi/	you (m.s.) intend
2. m. pl.	/tə-nw-u/	you (m.pl.) intend
2. f. s.	/tə-nw-i/	you (f.s.) intend
2. f. pl	/tə-nwei-n/	you (f.pl.) intend
3. m. s.	/ʔi-nwi/	he intends
3. m. pl	/ʔi-nw-u/	they (m.) intend
3. f. s.	/tə-nwi/	she intends
3. f. pl.	/tə-nwei-n/	they (f.) intend

Table 6. 69: The inflectional paradigm for the Form VIII verb /ʔi-ʕitwi/ ‘he gets obstinacy’

/ʔi-ʕitwi/ ‘he gets obstinacy’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ ʔən -ʕitwi/	I get obstinacy
1. p	/ ʔən -ʕitwi/	we get obstinacy
2. m. s	/t-ʕitwi/	you (m.s.) get obstinacy
2. m. pl.	/t-ʕitw-u/	you (m.pl.) get obstinacy
2. f. s.	/t-ʕitw-i/	you (f.s.) get obstinacy
2. f. pl	/t-ʕitwei-n/	you (f.pl.) get obstinacy
3. m. s.	/ʔi-ʕitwi/	he gets obstinacy
3. m. pl	/ʔi-ʕitw-u/	they (m.) get obstinacy
3. f. s.	/t-ʕitwi/	she gets obstinacy
3. f. pl.	/t-ʕitwei-n/	they (f.) get obstinacy

6.3.2 Quadrilateral Verbs

The quadrilateral stems, regular and reduplicated and the derived quadrilateral all have the schwa /ə/ as their final vowel. When they get inflected in the imperfect aspect by means of circumfixation, suffixes and prefixes, the schwa is moved or elided. It gets moved when the following suffix is a consonant-initial one. When the following suffix is a vowel-initial one the schwa gets elided. In the imperfect aspect, the regular and reduplicated quadrilaterals have the short vowel /a/ as their first vowel. In the imperfect aspect the schwa takes the place of the short vowel /a/ following the first radical. However, the short vowel /a/ is there in the imperfective stems of the quadrilateral derived verbs and it is not replaced. More clarification is provided by the following examples.

Table 6. 70: The inflectional paradigm for the regular quadrilateral verb /ʕəntʰiz/ ‘he shows off’

/ʕi-ʕəntʰiz/ ‘he shows off’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-ʕəntʰəz/	I show off
1. p	/ʔən-ʕəntʰəz/	we show off
2. m. s	/t-ʕəntʰəz/	you (m.s.) show off
2. m. pl.	/t-ʕəntʰz-u/	you (m.pl.) show off
2. f. s.	/t-ʕəntʰz-i/	you (f.s.) show off
2. f. pl	/t-ʕəntʰz-in/	you (f.pl.) show off
3. m. s.	/ʕi-ʕəntʰz/	he shows off
3. m. pl	/ʕi-ʕəntʰz-u/	they (m.) show off
3. f. s.	/t-ʕəntʰz/	she shows off
3. f. pl.	/t-ʕəntʰz-in/	they (f.) show off

Table 6. 71: The inflectional paradigm for the reduplicated quadrilateral verb /sʰərsʰir/ ‘he closes tight’

/ʕi-sʰərsʰir/ ‘he closes tight’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-sʰərsʰər/	I close tight
1. p	/ʔən-sʰərsʰər/	we close tight
2. m. s	/t-sʰərsʰər/	you (m.s.) close tight
2. m. pl.	/t-sʰərsʰr-u/	you (m.pl.) close tight
2. f. s.	/t-sʰərsʰr-i/	you (f.s.) close tight
2. f. pl	/t-sʰərsʰr-in/	you (f.pl.) close tight
3. m. s.	/ʕi-sʰərsʰr/	he close tight
3. m. pl	/ʕi-sʰərsʰr-u/	they (m.) close tight
3. f. s.	/t-sʰərsʰər/	she close tight
3. f. pl.	/t-sʰərsʰr-in/	they (f.) close tight

Table 6. 72: The inflectional paradigm for quadrilateral derived verb /trəs^ɹris^ɹ/ ‘he gets ordered’

/ʔi-trəs ^ɹ ris ^ɹ / ‘he gets ordered’	Imperfect	Gloss
1. s	/ʔən-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ /	I get ordered
1. p	/ʔən-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ /	we get ordered
2. m. s	/tə-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ /	you (m.s.) get ordered
2. m. pl.	/tə-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ -u/	you (m.pl.) get ordered
2. f. s.	/tə-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ -i/	you (f.s.) get ordered
2. f. pl	/tə-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ -in/	you (f.pl.) get ordered
3. m. s.	/ʔi-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ /	he gets ordered
3. m. pl	/ʔi-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ -u/	they (m.) get ordered
3. f. s.	/tə-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ /	she gets ordered
3. f. pl.	/tə-trəs ^ɹ rəs ^ɹ -in/	they (f.) get ordered

CHAPTER 7

SUMMARY and CONCLUSION

7.1 Introduction

This chapter begins by outlining a summary of the current thesis. Each chapter is summarized in simple words. Examples are used when necessary to insure more clarification is provided. At the end of this chapter the researcher concluded the study by highlighting the most important findings.

7.2 Summary

The first chapter of this thesis discusses the historical background of the Arabic Language as the current thesis investigates the verbal inflection of one of the Arabic dialects which is the Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin dialect. It gives an outline of the origins of the Arabic Language by presenting reliable views on this matter.

It tackles the statement of the problem. The researcher explores the need to document the target dialect. Abuata and Al-Omari (2014) stated that the importance of processing the dialects comes from here: “almost no native speakers of Arabic sustain continuous spontaneous production of Modern Standard Arabic. Standard Arabic is confined to formal written and spoken occasions, and the regional/social variety of Arabic is used at all other times (Watson, 2002). However, this is not the case for Arabic dialects and especially the Yemeni ones. Watson (2002), when she was investigating the Yemeni San’ani dialect, noted that San’ani is a dialect of the Arabian Peninsula, an area which has received little attention in generative work on the phonology and morphology of Arabic. This study is an attempt to document the verbal inflection of the Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin dialect.

In the same chapter, the researcher presents the research questions and the purpose of the study. Which is, to identify the verbal stems of HEBD, to identify what the verbs of HEBD are inflected for (tense, gender, etc.), and to describe how the HEBD verbs are inflected.

Chapter 2 carries out the definition of morphology and its two branches; derivational morphology and inflectional morphology in details. Since the current thesis is about the verbal inflection of an Arabic dialect, Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect, Arabic morphology was also discussed followed by an overview of Arabic verbs.

In the same chapter, the theoretical background of current study is clearly established. In this study, the verbal inflection of an Arabic dialect is investigated. Arabic belongs to a group of languages collectively known as the Semitic Languages (Versteegh, 2014). As a result, the non-concatenative templatic theory was adopted.

Chapter 2 is concluded by presenting the related literature on the Yemeni dialects, especially the Hadhrami ones. There has not been a study conducted on the Hadhrami Eastern Bedouin Dialect. The current study is considered to be the first study tackling a morphological aspect, the verbal inflection, of the target dialect.

Chapter 3 outlines the methodology and the research design of the current study. It is a qualitative research in which an ethnography approach was adopted. According to Creswell (2014) an ethnography is a qualitative strategy in which the researcher studies an intact cultural group in a natural setting over a prolonged period of time by collecting primarily observational and interview data.

Chapter 3 discusses sampling and selection of informants and data collection. Informal interviews, the Swadesh List, and oral morphology questionnaire were productive sources in collecting reliable data. The method of analysis used in analyzing the collected data is explained in the end of chapter 3.

Chapter 4 begins by describing the phonology of HEBD. Consonants and vowels of HEBD were presented. There are twenty seven phonemes in HBED. They are distributed as follows: eight stops (/b/, /t/, /t^ʕ/, /d/, /d^ʕ/, /k/, /g/, and /ʔ/), twelve fricatives (/θ/, /ð/, /f/, /s/, /s^ʕ/, /z/, /ʃ/, /χ/, /ʁ/, /ħ/, /ʕ/ and /h/), one affricative (/j/), two nasals (/m/ and /n/), one approximant (/l/) and one trill (/r/). /j/. Regarding the vowels, six short vowels (/ʌ/, /ɒ/, /a/, /i/, /ə/ and /u/),

six long vowels (/i:/, /ɔ:/, /ɑ:/, /u:/, /a:/ and /ɜ:/) and two diphthongs (/ai/ and /ei/) are found in HEBD. The chapter concluded by discussing the syllable structure of the current dialect and outlining the fourteen syllable pattern the collected data revealed.

Chapter 5 is devoted to a discussion of the verb measures found in HEBD which are fundamental in the study of the verbal inflection of this dialect. Being an Arabic dialect, The verbs measures were analyzed within the framework of MSA. Schulz (2004) stated that there are fifteen measures of which only ten are used in MSA. The collected data revealed that there are eight measures for the trilateral verbs and only two in which quadrilateral verbs are realized.

Chapter 6 is the most important one where the data of verbal inflection of the HEBD were analysed. It is divided into two sections: the perfect aspect and the imperfect aspect. In each aspect, HEBD verbs inflect for gender, number and person. This verbal inflection is achieved by means of prefixation in the perfect aspect and prefixation and suffixation in the imperfect aspect. In most cases, a vocalic change is a must in the verbal inflection of the HEBD. The following example from HEBD shows how new forms are derived through phonological operations:

Perfect (past, complete); (Root)	Imperfect (non-past, incomplete)
[drdr] He 3 rd . s. m. hung out	[ʕidardar] He 3 rd . s. m. is hanging out

7.3 Conclusion

The current study that investigates the verbal inflection of HEBD set out to:

- 1) Identify the verbal stems of HEBD.

2) Describe how verbs of HEBD are inflected for gender, number and person.

With regard to the first objective, it is concerned with the identification of most possible inflected verbs in HEBD. It has been achieved through various instruments such as the oral morphology questionnaire, informal interviews and recording of spontaneous speech, that were used in collecting the data for the current study. The gathered data were first classified and examined carefully.

To achieve the second and the third objectives, the classified data were analysed using the Non-concatenative Templatic Theory which was proposed by McCarthy (1979 and 1981). The analysis of the data revealed that:

1) HEBD stems are formed within eight Measures. Measure IV and IX of Arabic have no counterpart in HEBD.

2) Some stems of Measure I are realized with more than one stem vowel.

3) The Schwa /ə/ is used extensively in forming the HEBD verbs.

4) HEBD verbs are inflected in two aspects; the perfect aspect and the imperfect aspect. This inflection is achieved through means of prefixes, suffixes, and infixes. Moreover, a vocalic change is there in most cases. Through the process of inflection, those affixes carry out information about gender, number and person.

5) HEBD, as an Arabic dialect, adopts the system of non-concatenative morphology of the Semitic languages and dialects. Some stems take the diphthong /ei/ when they are inflected for the 1 and the 2 in the imperfect aspect. According to Booij (2007, p. 37):

An interesting kind of non-concatenative morphology is found in, among others,

Semitic languages: root-and-pattern morphology. The basis of each lexeme is a skeleton of consonants, in most cases three, which functions as the root of the lexeme. The abstract pattern of consonants is combined with one or more vowels, which are intertwined with the sequence of consonants. In addition, the lexeme may contain a prefix and a suffix.

The following figure explore the non-concatenative morphology of HEBD verbal inflection by providing an example of a sound verb of Measure II which take the diphthong /ei/.

Figure 7.1: The pattern of the triliteral geminate stem /yæssəl/: “to wash” after adding the personal suffix /tu/: “2m.pl”.

6) Some other verbs of HEBD do not take the diphthong /ei/ as they inflect for 1st person and

is recommended.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX A

Oral morphology questionnaire

A. The Verb phrase:

1 Present

1.1. I (c.)

1.2. you (m.sg.)

1.3. you (f.sg.)

1.4. he / she / it

is walking / is not walking

1.5. we (c.)

1.6. you (m.pl.)

1.7. you (f.pl.)

1.8. they (m.pl.)

1.2. My cow is dead. What shall I do?.

1.3. Will he arrive tomorrow? Yes, he will arrive tomorrow. No, he will not arrive tomorrow, but the day after.

1.4. Who will go? I will go. Nobody will go.

1.5. He will come this evening.

1.6. He will come tomorrow.

1.7. He will come next year.

1.8. He is going to leave any moment now.

4. Indicative

1.1. He is going. He is coming. He is running.

1.2. He is eating.

1.3. He is eating gruel.

1.4. He is opening.

1.5. He is opening the door.

2. Narrative

2.1. Yesterday I went to a grocery shop, I bought some grain, I brought it home to my wife, I told her to cook it, she cooked it and we ate it.

2.2. tomorrow I will go to a grocery shop, I will buy some grain, I will bring it home to my wife, I will tell her to cook it, and we will eat it.

3. Subjunctive

3.1. I want to beat you.

3.2. We do not want to die.

3.3. He intends to come.

3.4. He intended to come and see us.

3.5. He tried to jump and fell.

4. Potential

4.1. He is able to come.

4.2. He is not able to come.

4.3. He is able to walk in spite of his illness.

4.4. He cannot read; he is blind.

4.5. He cannot speak; he is dumb.

5. Permissive

5.1. May I come tomorrow?

5.2. May I come and play with you?

6. Obligative

6.1. You must eat in order to grow.

6.2. There is nothing to do but to go and look for him.

6.3. You must do it.

7. Imperative

7.1. Sing! Don't sing!

7.2. Let him sing! Let him not sing!

7.3. Don't sing, be quiet; people are sleeping.

7.4. Go right away; you are going to be late.

7.5. Don't go; it's going to rain.

7.6. Let him leave; I don't want to see him again.

7.7. Leave quickly!

7.8. Don't leave!

7.9. Let them go; they weary me.

8. Purposive

1.1 He went to have a drink of water. I came to see my sister.

1.2 He took your spear to kill some dog.

1.3 I will give you a knife to kill the chicken.

1.4 The old woman gave her son poison so that he would die.

9. Interrogative

9.1. Is he coming?

- 9.2. Has anyone seen him?
- 9.3. What are you doing?
- 9.4. What is he doing?
- 9.5. What is he eating?
- 9.6. Who gave you that garment?
- 9.7. Who is coming here?
- 9.8. Who told you that the chief had left?
- 9.9. How did you catch it?
- 9.10. How do you say it?
- 9.11. Which one did you catch?
- 9.12. which one of the two do you want?
- 9.13. Where did you catch it?
- 9.14. Where did he go buy?
- 9.15. Where is he going?
- 9.16. Where is he coming from?
- 9.17. How many of them did you catch?
- 9.18. How long did you stay?
- 9.19. Why did you go to the village?

9.20. Why are you crying?

9.21. Why did you leave?

9.22. When are you coming?

9.23. When did you catch it?

9.24. Until when are you staying?

10. Passive

10.1. Why is the child screaming? Because he is being beaten.

10.2. Where is the meat? It has been eaten.

10.3. Where is the dog? It's dead. How did it die? It was killed by a blow from a spear. It was caught by a man.

10.4. The pot broke. The water spilled. The rope came untied. This pot was broken by the child. The water was spilled. The rope was untied.

11. Reciprocal

11.1. The two men killed each other.

11.2. We will kill each other.

11.3. The children are fighting against one another.

12. Reflexive

12.1. The man killed himself. The two men (each) killed themselves.

12.2. We shall kill ourselves.

12.3. The children are (each) beating themselves.

12.4. The child wounded himself with his knife.

13. Transitive – Intransitive

13.1. What are you doing? I'm not doing anything.

13.2. What are you (pl.) doing? We are not doing anything.

13.3. I am sitting down. I am walking.

13.4. I am cooking.

13.5. We are Mehri.

13.6. What are the people doing? The people are dancing, moving about, quarrelling.

13.7. What are you cooking? I am cooking meat.

13.8. Are you (pl.) sleeping? No, we are just lying down.

13.9. He is drinking - He is eating - He is running.

14. Causative

14.1. The man woke up. The child woke the man up.

14.2. The baby is feeding at the breast. The mother is making the baby feed (at her breast).

14.3. The boy is drinking some water. I made the boy drink some water. I let the boy drink some water.

15. Habitual

15.1. What do the Mehri men do?

- 15.2. The Mehri men do the hunting, fishing.
- 15.3. What do the Mehri women do? The Mehri women prepare the food.
- 15.4. The child has fallen asleep. The child is asleep now. The child sleeps everyday.
- 15.5. It is the men who hunt.
16. Simultaneous
- 16.1. She sings while grinding the grain.
- 16.2. She laughs while preparing the food.
- 16.3. He weaves a mat while telling me a story.
17. Completive – incomplete
- 1.1 Do you see a car over there? Yes, I see it. No, I don't see it.
- 1.2 Can you see something inside? Yes, I can. No. I can't.
- 1.3 I have finished the work.
- 1.4 She has finished grinding the grain.
- 1.5 He has arrived.
- 1.6 I am finishing the work.
- 1.7 I have not finished the work
18. Conditional
- 18.1. He will not come if it rains.

- 18.2. If the child loses the sheep, his father will beat him.
- 18.3. If you stay here, you will be killed.
- 18.4. If you had stayed here, you would have been killed.
19. Directional
- 19.1. Go (2m.sg.) away. Go (2m.pl.) away!
- 19.2. Go (2f.sg.) away. Go (2f.pl.) away!
- 19.3. Run (2m.sg.)! Run (2m.pl.)! (away from me)
- 19.4. Drag the log away from me!
- 19.5. Go down into the well over there!
- 19.6. Climb up that tree over there!
- 19.7. Come (2m.sg.) here! Come (2m.pl.) here!
- 19.8. Come (2f.sg.) here! Come (2f.pl.) here!
- 19.9. Run (2m.sg.)! Run (2m.pl.)! (toward me)
- 19.10. Run (2f.sg.)! Run (2f.pl.)! (toward me)
- 19.11. Drag the log toward me!
- 19.12. Come down from the tree and come here!
- 19.13. Come out of the well!
- 19.14. Give me the money back!

19.15. Give him the money back!

19.16. Give them the money back!

20. Reference to source and goal

20.1. He will become a fisherman.

20.2. He will become a harvester.

21. Progressive

21.1. He is getting dressed.

21.2. He is getting undressed so that he can wash.

21.3. She tied up the goat.

21.4. She untied the goat.

APPENDIX B

Swadesh List of HEBD

The list below shows 100 items on the Swadesh list of HEBD

No	English	HEBD
1	I, me	/na/
2	you	/ntəh/
3	we	/nhə/
4	this	/da/
5	that	/da:k/
6	who	/mən/
7	what	/weɪʃ/, /ʔeɪʃ/
8	not	/la/
9	all	/kul/
10	many	/yəzi/, /wəied/, /yum/

11	one	/waħid/
12	two	/thnein/
13	big	/kbər/
14	long	/t ^s wi:l/
15	small	/gs ^s ɜr/
16	woman	/marəh/
17	man	/rəʒal/
18	person	/waħid
19	fish	/s ^s eid.s ^s ɣɜr/
20	bird	/t ^s ɜr/
21	dog	/kalb/
22	louse	/gimləh/
23	tree	/ʃarah/
24	seed	ˈdəri/
25	leaf	/wargəh/
26	root	/ʒədər/
27	bark	/giʃrəh
28	skin	/ʒəld/

29	flesh	/laħm/
30	blood	/dɔm/
31	bone	/ʕadʕəm/
32	grease	/ʃaħəm/
33	egg	/bɔdʕ/
34	horn	/garn/
35	tail	/deil/
36	feather	/ri:ʃəh/
37	hair	/ʃaħr/
38	head	/ra:s/
39	ear	/du:n/
40	eye	/ʕein/
41	nose	/nuħrəh/
42	mouth	/fum/
43	tooth	/dʕars/
44	tongue	/lsɜn/
45	claw	/dʕaifu:r/
46	foot	/riɜl/

47	knee	/ruk bə h/
48	hand	/yad/
49	belly	/bat ʕ n/
50	neck	/rə g bəh/
51	breast(s)	/s ʕ idər/
52	heart	/galb/
53	liver	/kbəd/
54	to drink	/ʃrəb/
55	to eat	/kal/
56	to bite	/ʕad ʕ /
57	to see	/ʃɜ:f/
58	to hear	/smə ʕ /
59	to know	/h sə /
60	to sleep	/n ʕəs /
61	to die	/mɜ:t/
62	to kill	/gtəl
63	to swim	/sbə ħ /
64	to fly	/far/

65	to walk	/wɒk/
66	to come	/kʌm/
67	to lie	/laɪ/
68	to sit	/sɪt/
69	to stand	/stænd/
70	to fall	/fɔːl/
71	to say	/seɪ/
72	sun	/sʌn/
73	moon	/muːn/
74	star	/stɑː/
75	water	/wɔːtə/
76	rain	/reɪn/
77	stone	/steɪn/
78	sand	/sænd/
79	earth	/ɜːθ/
80	cloud	/klaʊd/
81	smoke	/sməʊk/
82	fire	/faɪə/

83	ash	/rma:d/
84	burn	/ħreig/
85	path	/t ^s reig/
86	mountain	/ʒbal/
87	red	/ħmar/
88	green	/χd ^s ar/
89	yellow	/s ^s far/
90	white	/biəd ^s /
91	black	/suəd
92	night	/leil/
93	hot, warm	/ħar/
94	cold	/bɜrəd/
95	full	mlɜ:n/
96	new	/ʒdi:d/
97	good	/tmaam/, /reid ^s /
98	round	/mdawər/
99	dry	/yɜbəs/
100	name	/ʔəsəm/

APPENDX C

Pictures of HEBD Regions

Plate 7. 1: a picture of a wedding ceremony in Ghail bin Yomain

Plate 7. 2: a picture of the village of Halfoon in Ad Dais Alsharqiah

Plate 7. 3: a picture of the village of Maaber in Qusaiir

Plate 7. 4: An Afternoon Social Gathering in Asad Aljabal